

Co-UDlabs

Building Collaborative Urban Drainage
research Labs communities

D2.4. Final report on staff development

Date of delivery - 25/04/2025

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This project has received funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
under grant agreement N° 101008626

DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Starting date	01.05.2021
Duration	48 months
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Deliverable Information	
Deliverable number	D2.4
Work package number	WP2
Deliverable title	Final report on staff development
Lead beneficiary	Euronovia
Authors	Laura De Nale (Euronovia), Alma Schellart (USFD)
Due date	30/04/2025
Actual submission date	25/04/2025
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

VERSION MANAGEMENT

Revision history and quality check			
Version	Name	Date	Comment
V 0.1	Laura De Nale, Euronovia	01/04/2025	First draft
V 0.2	Alma Schellart, USFD	17/04/2024	Contributions and updates
V 1.0	Laura De Nale, Euronovia, Alma Schellart, USFD	25/04/2024	Revision and updates. Final version

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Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Co-UDlabs aims to create a urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

List of acronyms

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CSO	Combined Sewer Overflow
DIC	Digital Image Correlation
DMP	Data Management Plan
EPSRC	Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (United Kingdom)
ICUD	International Conference of Urban Drainage
IOT	Internet Of Things
IWA	International Water Association
JRA	Joint Research Activity
LSPIV	Large-Scale Particle Image Velocimetry
OFWAT	The Office of Water Services (United Kingdom)
PIV	Particle Image Velocimetry
PLS	Partial Least Squares
RI	Research Infrastructure
SOM	Self Organizing Maps
SuDS	Sustainable Drainage System
TA	Transnational Access
UDMT	Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox
UDRAIN	Large Research Infrastructure in Urban Drainage Working Group
UDS	Urban Drainage System
UK EDM	United Kingdom's Event Duration Monitoring database
UWWTD	Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive
WP	Work Package
WWTW	Wastewater Treatment Works

Executive summary

This document is a deliverable of the Co-UDlabs project, funded under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008626.

Deliverable 2.4 is the final report on development and mobility of personnel staff of Co-UDlabs, that took place among partners of the consortium to build internal capacity relevant to Transnational Access and Joint Research Activities by facilitating the exchange of know-how and best practices among the project staff members and the participants working in the RIs. The main topics of the visits were:

- See different SuDS monitoring methods (14 visits) and SuDS modelling methods (5 visits)
- Demonstrate and see different sewer inspection techniques (8 visits), asset deterioration laboratory testing techniques (2 visits).
- See different optical water quality monitoring techniques (10 visits)
- See different methods for Particle Imaging Velocimetry techniques (5 visits), and alternative techniques for flow, flow depth and/or velocity monitoring (3 visits)
- Discuss available data and non-available data related to combined sewer overflows (6 visits)
- Different methods for exchanging laboratory data and data harmonization techniques (6 visits)
- Several visits also discussed how urban drainage data is used in regulatory frameworks, as well as gaps between science and policy making (5 visits)

Other topics were micropollutants monitoring, micro-plastic and macro-plastic transport analysis, multiphase flow mixing issues, urban flooding measurement and simulation, rainfall generators, H₂S monitoring, urban drainage systems and soils interaction measurements, sewer rehabilitation techniques. General discussions were held about future developments and challenges facing urban drainage systems during several visits.

In total, the partners went through 41 missions, counting for a total of 147 person-days of mobility, corresponding to 29.4 weeks. Most of the visits took place during the 2nd reporting period (21 visits), with only 5 visits during the 1st reporting period and 15 visits during the 3rd reporting period. USFD and EAWAG are the partners with the highest number of mobilities implemented, with EAWAG taking part in the longest mission, having stayed 30 days at UDC to carry out rainfall-runoff experiments in the context of SuDS. AAU only conducted 1 visit, as it was found that all the envisaged objectives could be covered during this visit, as well as during meetings taking place on the occasion of physical consortium meetings and through online meetings.

Sending

	<i>UDC</i>	<i>UFSD</i>	<i>DEL</i>	<i>EAWAG</i>	<i>IKT</i>	<i>INSA</i>	<i>AaU</i>
<i>UDC</i>		6 days		42 days	4 days		1 day
<i>UFSD</i>			7 days		6 days	4 days	
<i>DEL</i>	3,5 days	8 days					
<i>EAWAG</i>		8 days			4 days		
<i>IKT</i>	8 days	24 days				5,5 days	
<i>INSA</i>		4 days		2 days	13 days		
<i>AaU</i>	3 days	3 days				2,5 days	

Table 1 – Overview of the Co-UDlabs staff mobility (in person days).

1. Staff mobility plan

To provide optimal services to the Transnational Access users, the relevant staff of the consortium had to be proficient in data harmonization and interoperability methods. The aim of staff mobility was to build internal capacity relevant to Transnational Access and Joint Research Activities and ensure that each partner could master a variety of experimental techniques. This activity also supported the networking and trust between all partners, stimulated exchange, development and inspired new ideas for improved quality and services.

Staff mobilities were performed according to the following agreed procedures:

- Prior to respective assignments of personnel, the sending partner specified the planned activities of the staff as well as the purpose and duration of the mission.
- The hosting partner was responsible for enabling the implementation of the assigned person's tasks, including the granting of necessary access to facilities and was also responsible for the respective working and safety conditions.
- The sending partner supported the costs incurred for the personnel mission (travel, accommodation and living expenses), using their own defined budget.
- After completion of the mission, the assigned person wrote a report on his/her activities during the mission, which was sent to Euronovia (task leader) after being approved by the coordinator of his/her research group. These reports are included in this deliverable.

Below is the Co-UDlabs mobility plan, as was described at the proposal stage. It included 38,25 weeks of mobility among partners.

		Sending						
		<i>UDC</i>	<i>USFD</i>	<i>DEL</i>	<i>EAWAG</i>	<i>IKT</i>	<i>INSA</i>	<i>AaU</i>
Hosting	<i>UDC</i>		2		1	2		2
	<i>USFD</i>	1		2	0,5	2	1	
	<i>DEL</i>	1	2			2		
	<i>EAWAG</i>	1	2				1	
	<i>IKT</i>	1	2	2			1	
	<i>INSA</i>	1	2		0,75			2
	<i>AaU</i>	1	2				1	

Table 2 – Overview of the original Co-UDlabs staff mobility plan (in weeks).

2. Staff mobility implementation

It is to be noted that staff mobility activities and visits were re-organised and re-scheduled after the project launch, to be shorter but more frequent than originally planned at the proposal stage (i.e. some days to one week duration). This is due to three main reasons: 1) The staff mobility plan was drafted before the Covid-19 pandemics, when collaborations took place mainly face-to-face, and when people were not used to working online as much as they are now. 2) Especially in the first year after the project launch, travel was very limited due to Covid restrictions; 3) With the spread of online communication tools, which became widely used after Covid-19, it was agreed that, in order to optimize the use of resources, some of the envisaged activities could be successfully carried out remotely among partners.

Although the planned capacity-building did not follow the original schedule, there have been many collaborations among partners throughout the project, including new opportunities not envisaged in the original schedule. Also, because some partners (UDC, INSA Lyon, EAWAG, IKT) hosted four of the project's General Assemblies with laboratory tours prior to the General Assembly, consortium members could take advantage of these travels to visit facilities, discuss ongoing collaborations, and work on joint tasks.

An overview of the mobility implementation is shown in Annex 1, and a report of each mobility session is provided in Annex 2.

2.1. Overview of staff mobility visit activities

A wide range of activities were carried out during the mobility visits, including laboratory and field site visits, testing other partners novel monitoring equipment, models, and data sharing methods. A lot of discussion about ongoing and new challenges in urban drainage and discussion of ongoing as well as potential future research took place. See also Figure 1 for a word-cloud overview.

Many visits concerned different SuDS monitoring methods (14 visits) and SuDS modelling methods (5 visits). There were 13 person-days of visit starting exciting new collaborations between IKT and INSA on SuDS monitoring capability which were not in the original plan.

Many visits also centered around demonstration of different sewer inspection techniques (8 visits), and asset deterioration laboratory testing techniques (2 visits), this led also to new opportunities of testing monitoring techniques developed at USFD in IKTs full-scale test facility.

A collaboration is still ongoing on comparing different optical water quality monitoring techniques (10 visits), due to European and worldwide concerns around surface and groundwater quality, the consortium has brought together their experiences on different novel optical techniques.

Several visits also concerned specifically Particle Imaging Velocimetry techniques (5 visits), and alternative techniques for flow, flow depth and/or velocity monitoring (3 visits).

Collaborations are also still ongoing on different methods of monitoring combined sewer overflows (6 visits), and different levels of sharing combined sewer overflow performance data.

Although all visits allowed the partners to explore each other's methods for data management, 6 visits specifically focused only on intercomparing different techniques for exchanging laboratory data and data harmonization.

Several visits also discussed how urban drainage data is used in regulatory frameworks, as well as gaps between science and policy making (5 visits). This led to several ongoing collaborations and a policy paper.

1. Annex 1. Summary of Co-UDlabs mobilities

Sending partner	Hosting institution	Duration (in days)	Staff #1	Staff #2	Staff #3	Staff #4	N. of person-days	Purpose of the mission	Related WP	Date
UDC	DELTARES	3,5	Juan NAVES				3.5	Sharing experiences about imaging techniques for UDS	WP8	22/04/2024 to 25/04/2024
UDC	IKT	4	Jose ANTA	Joaquín SUÁREZ			8	Share experiences on permeable pavement testing	WP8	12/06/23 to 15/06/23
UDC	AaU	3	Juan NAVES				3	Installation of LSPIV equipment in the Aalborg retention pond	WP8	24/10/2022 to 28/10/2022
USFD	UDC	3	Kaeli Brazier	James Shucksmith			6	Learn about experiment standardisation Collaboration UDC-USFD on Task 8.2	WP8	14/06/2023 to 16/06/2023
USFD	DELTARES	2	Alma Schellart (1day)	James Shucksmith (2 days)			3	Learn more about remote sensing techniques, and relevance to spatial analysis of surface water quality and CSO performance analysis. Discuss optical sensing techniques, and coordinate WP6 activities on this topic. Learn more about facilities at Deltares	WP6	04/04/2024 to 05/04/2024
USFD	EAWAG	3	Isabel Douterelo				3	Visit urban water observatory and discuss research possibilities in relation with water quality issues	WP6	21/01/2024 to 24/01/2024
USFD	EAWAG	2	Alma Schellart				2	Collaboration on open CSO data, learn from Swiss & UK practice	WP6	09/11/23 to 10/11/23
USFD	EAWAG	3	Yiqi Wu				3	joint development and implementation of simulation models to assess the impact of pipe defects on the hydraulic performance of sewer networks	WP7	02/04/2025 to 04/04/2025

USFD	IKT	3	Simon Tait				3	Technical knowledge exchange and investigation of feasibility of developing project submission for latest EU calls.	WP7	10/10/22 to 12/10/22
USFD	IKT	3	Simon Tait				3	Discussing test setup WP7 (JRA2) and next steps Visit IKT facilities and discuss test and measurement technique Plan webinar “Inspection techniques” (WP3) Information exchange WP1,2,3,4,9 Information exchange on challenges (e.g. climate change, aging infrastructure) for UD in GER, the UK and associated countries	WP7	13/12/2023 to 15/12/2023
USFD	INSA	2	James Shucksmith				2	Discussion of WP8 and exchange of best practices	WP8	01/09/2022 to 02/09/2022
USFD	INSA	2	Alma Schellart				2	Collaboration on open CSO data, learn from French & UK practice	WP6	06/11/23 to 07/11/23
USFD	AaU	1	Henriette Jensen				1	Learn about techniques for microplastics quantification	WP6	16/04/24 to 17/04/24
USFD	IKT	3	Simon Tait				3	WP7 task planning, webinar planning, support dissemination event	WP7	10/09/24 to 12/09/24
USFD	DELTARES	2	Alma Schellart	Yiqi Wu			4	Knowledge exchange on England and Wales Spatial Combined Sewer Overflow data, and spatial correlation analysis methods.	WP6	19/01/25 to 20/01/25
USFD	IKT	4	Gavin Sailor				4	Coordination regarding the implementation of the tests of WP 7 (JRA2), Task 7.2, Instruction of IKT staff in the use of an inspection system developed by USFD	WP7	03/06/2024 to 06/06/2024

USFD	AaU	2,5	Isabel Dourtelo				2.5	Visit the research facilities at AAU. Discuss a future EU Doctoral Network proposal with AAU participation.		16/06/24 to 19/06/24
USFD	IKT	3	Simon Tait				3	Information exchange about DIC joint measurements, collaboration on asset deterioration	WP7	02/04/25 to 04/04/25
USFD	IKT	4	Gavin Sailor				4	Information exchange about DIC joint measurements, collaboration on asset deterioration	WP7	01/04/24 to 04/04/2525
USFD	IKT	4	Gavin Sailor				4	Information exchange about DIC joint measurements, carrying out full scale DIC joint measurements in lined pipe	WP7	22/04/25 to 25/04/25
DELTARES	USFD	4	François Clemens				4	Collaboration on open CSO data, learn from UK practice, publication on optical sewer monitoring techniques	WP6	17/4/23 to 21/04/2023
DELTARES	USFD	2	Antonio Moreno	Danko Boonstra			4	Purpose of the mission: Learn about the Laboratory of the university of Sheffield Learn about administrative protocols for data collection and storage of the facilities Learn about techniques used at the Laboratory of Sheffield Share experience with experimental work and methods (presentations)	WP6	27/06/23 to 29/06/23
EAWAG	UDC	6	Prabhat Joshi				6	Collaboration on green roof/ SUDS	WP8	07/05/2023 to 12/05/2023
EAWAG	UDC	30	Prabhat Joshi				30	Collaboration on green roof/ SUDS, Collaboration on Blue-Green campus at Eawag/EMPA	WP8	18/09/2023 to 18/10/2023
EAWAG	UDC	2	Pierre LECHEVALIER				2	Knowledge transfer spectrometry and sewer monitoring	WP6	31/01/2024 to 03/02/2024
EAWAG	INSA	2	Pierre LECHEVALIER				2	Knowledge transfer spectrometry and sewer monitoring	WP6	20/09/2021 to 21/09/2021

EAWAG	UDC	4	Alfredo Chavarria				4	Data harmonization	WP2	06/11/23 to 10/11/23
IKT	UDC	4	Marcel Goerke				4	Collaboration on SUDS: clogging of permeable pavement and green roofs (JRA 3)	WP8	14/11/23 to 17/11/23
IKT	INSA	2	Marcel Goerke				2	Collaboration on SUDS: green roofs	WP8	16/09/2024 to 17/09/2024
IKT	USFD	2	Thomas Brüggemann	Yongxiang Qiao			4	Collaboration on deterioration assets	WP7	16/09/2024 to 18/09/2024
IKT	EAWAG	2	Thomas Brüggemann	Bert Bosseler			4	Knowledge transfer SUDS / data harmonization	WP2	02/09/2024 to 03/09/2024
IKT	USFD	1	Ashwini Ausekar	Iain Naismith			2	Knowledge transfer "Deterioration Assets"	WP7	21/11/2024
IKT	INSA	3	Marcel Goerke	Frank Bersuck	Simon Torunski		9	Collaboration on SUDS	WP8	27/11/23 to 29/11/23
IKT	INSA	0,5	Thomas Brüggemann	Marcel Goerke	Matteo Rubinato	Bert Bosseler	2	Mutual presentation and exploration of possible future collaborations.		01/09/2022
IKT	INSA	2,0	Marcel Goerke				2	Joining work of TA IndoorGRASP Visit of INSA facility GROOF and JRA-research of 1x1 m Discussion and analysing the data of first measurements Planning next steps of common work.		25/02/25 to 26/02/25
INSA	USFD	4	Frédéric Cherqui				4	Knowledge transfer pipe condition assessment technologies	WP7	16/04/23 to 21/04/23
INSA	IKT	0,5	Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski				0.5	Mutual presentation and further collaboration.		09/01/2023

INSA	IKT	2,5	Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski				2.5	Green roof experiments and modelling (continuation of 1st visit in January 2023)	WP6	10/07/23 to 12/07/23
INSA	IKT	2,5	Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski				2.5	Green roof experiments related to TA Indoor-Grasp (WP9) & Presentation of Co-UDlabs project (related to WP4) & Participation to the IKT 30th Anniv. International conference "Sewers for the 21st century - II"	WP2	10/09/24 to 12/09/24
INSA	AaU	2,5	Gislain Lipeme-Kouyi				2.5	Infiltration processes	WP8	10/07/23 to 12/07/23
AaU	UDC	1	Jesper Ellerbæk Nielsen				1	Learn about techniques for LSPIV measurement and IOT technology for SUDS performance	WP8	24/03/2025 to 25/03/2025

TOT.
days 148
TOT.
weeks 29.4

Table 3 – Detailed overview of Co-UDlabs mobilities

2. ANNEX 2 Mobility session reports

2.1. EAWAG to INSA (September 2021)

From (dd/mm/yy):	20/09/2021
To (dd/mm/yy):	21/09/2021
Duration (in days):	2
Purpose of the mission:	<p>Knowledge transfer for i) optical water quality monitoring methods in sewers, i.e. using submerged spectrometers and turbidity sensors, ii) data quality control and uncertainty analysis and iii) the organization of Task 6.1 (T6.1).</p> <p>Knowledge transfer in the field of spectrometry helps to advance the current skills in Co-UDlabs by allowing researchers from Eawag and practitioners to build on the work of INSA and others. By sharing information and experiences, we pave the way for the development of new methods, techniques, and technologies that are more effective and efficient.</p> <p>Also, knowledge transfer is essential for maintaining quality control in Co-UDlabs. By sharing information about best practices and quality standards between Eawag and INSA, we ensure that our work meets the highest standards of accuracy and reliability.</p> <p>Ultimately, this mission was vital for the ultimate goal of Co-UDlabs to promote innovation in spectrometry and sewer monitoring. Specifically, Eawag is developing and testing non-contact monitoring approaches using Hyperspectral images (T6.1, WP9). By sharing new ideas and technologies, we contribute to developing new approaches to problem-solving and push the boundaries of what is possible in the field.</p>
Planned activities:	<p><u>Day 1: 20 September 2021</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Morning: visit of the monitoring site of Chassieu, close to Lyon, including a presentation of the testing bench: wastewater pumping, sensor installation and maintenance. • Afternoon: meeting with Co-UDlabs partner to discuss about of WP6.2 <p><u>Day 2: 21 September 2021</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Morning: knowledge transfer about spectrometry and the operation and maintenance of submerged spectrometers, the installation of their S::CAN probes and monitoring of suspended solids. • Afternoon: work for WP6.1: selection of 6 sensors and planning of future tasks.

Figure 1 - (top) The stormwater monitoring station of INSA at their Chassieu field laboratory, which uses a bypass system to facilitate the installation and maintenance of online sensors to continuously monitor stormwater quality (bottom) Overview of the site.

Main achievements and challenges:

Work for WP6:

Previously, INSA gathered from the consortium a list of 55 sensors to be tested in the framework of the Co-UDlabs project. As leaders of the corresponding T6.1, INSA (Jean-Luc, Mathieu) and Eawag (Jörg Rieckermann, Pierre Lechevallier) met online to critically analyze the 55 propositions. The aim of this analysis was to identify sensors that fulfilled the project's criteria, i.e. novelty, feasibility, and relevance. A list of 15 sensors was selected (see Deliverable 6.1).

The next step was to plan for the coordination of further actions. It was agreed to organize a vote among the project's institutions to select 8 sensors that would be tested as part of the project. The coordination of the testing phase will also involve selecting leader for the testing of each 8 sensors.

Knowledge transfer:

	<p>Mathieu Lepot shared his experience with Pierre over a period of two days. First, they visited the stormwater monitoring station of Chassieu, in particular to discuss about their online monitoring station. This included information about wastewater pumping, data collection, sensor maintenance, and data analysis. This information very relevant, as Pierre is planning to use a similar facility at the HALL infrastructure of Eawag, the experimental flume.</p> <p>Second, they discussed about the analysis of spectrometric data, with a particular focus on the Spectrolyser (S::CAN) submerged spectrometer sensor. This sensor is commonly used for on-site absorbance measurement and is also available at Eawag.</p> <p>Finally, Mathieu discussed the measurement of suspended solids using an online turbidity probe. He emphasized the importance of building a site-specific calibration curve for accurate results.</p>
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services:	<p>As Pierre Lechevallier was in the beginning of his work for Eawas and Co-UDlabs, the main objective was to get to transfer the knowledge on the maintenance, calibration and data handling of the submerged spectrometer probes. One important lesson was that, for data analysis, the best-performing method was PArTial Least Squares (PLS) and that more advanced data driven methods, such as Random Forest or Neural Network approaches do not seem to provide better predictions from the observed absorbance spectra.</p> <p>In addition, the Eawag researcher got to know the INSA partners and how they organize their work, especially regarding the continuous stormwater monitoring and handling of monitoring data. In this, the onsite visits were especially valuable to discuss specific challenges and solutions.</p> <p>Last, but not least, this onsite meeting helped to plan the work package 6.1 more efficiently.</p>

2.2. USFD to INSA (September 2022)

From (dd/mm/yy):	01/09/2022
To (dd/mm/yy):	02/09/2022
Duration (in days):	2
Purpose of the mission:	The objective of the mission was to meet and discuss WP8 activities with representatives from UDC, IKT and Lyon. In addition, partners took the opportunity to attend the 1st Symposium on Urban Flood Experiments that was an expert-group event hosted by INSA Lyon on 1-2 September 2022.
Planned activities:	Workshop discussion, presentations, inspection of laboratory facilities and consideration of future work activities.
Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing of the current state of the art in measurement techniques and modelling associated with urban flooding; • Planning the activities of PhD students to be recruited at USFD in 2023; • Discussing the use of bespoke PIV particles produced at INSA Lyon for use at USFD facilities.
Comments:	Potential for greater collaboration was explored. This will be carried forward through more regular WP8 meetings.

2.3. IKT to INSA (September 2022)

From (dd/mm/yy):	01/09/2022
To (dd/mm/yy):	01/09/2022
Duration (in days):	0,5 (morning)
Purpose of the mission:	<p>1st visit of IKT at INSA Lyon, held on 01 September 2022 in the morning, for mutual presentation and exploration of possible future collaborations.</p> <p>Visitors: Thomas Brüggemann, Marcel Goerke, Bert Bosseler and Matteo Rubinato.</p>
Planned activities:	Presentations and visits
Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of INSA Lyon (laboratory DEEP) activities in the field of urban drainage and hydrology (Figure 2). • Visit of the GROOF platform on the INSA campus for experiments on green roofs • Visit of the OTHU SUDs facilities on the INSA campus (porous parking, infiltration trench and swale) for experiments on stormwater management.
	<p>The photograph shows five men standing in a room with bookshelves. In the foreground, a man in a dark green polo shirt with a white logo is smiling. Behind him are four other men in various attire, including a white shirt, a dark jacket, and a blue suit. They are all looking towards the camera.</p>
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services:	Greatest potential collaboration has been identified on the topic of green roofs.

Figure 2 – Group photo of the visit of IKT at INSA Lyon on 01/09/2022

2.4. USFD to IKT (October 2022)

From (dd/mm/yy):	10/10/22
To (dd/mm/yy):	12/10/22
Duration (in days):	3
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organising and coordinating cooperation within WP7 (JRA 2) between IKT and USFD in detail • Examining current EU calls and other funding sources. Aim to learn different bidding approaches and constraints. • Examining potential synergies between funded projects at both IKT and USFD
Planned activities:	<p><u>Day 1: 10th October 2022</u> (Simon Tait, Iain Naismith, Thomas Bruggemann)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe historical activities at IKT and USFD and current facilities, and identify potential collaborative opportunities • Examine the exchange of knowledge on pipe defect manufacture – see photographs below. <p><u>Day 2: 11th October 2022</u> (Simon Tait, Iain Naismith, Bert Bossler, Thomas Bruggemann)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss links with EU knowledge organisations (e.g. Eureau/EWA/Water Europe) • Consider Horizon CL5-2022-04-02-01 call. Hold brainstorming workshop and produce project concept note <p><u>Day 3 - 12th October 2022:</u> <i>Participants: Simon Tait, Thomas Bruggemann (part), Iain Naismith, Ton Bennan (part-online), Irene Scheperboer (part), Yongxiang Qian (part)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online meeting/discussion on TA AIR project to be held IKT and potential future links to current work in UK. • Discuss potential to link with UK pipebots project. • Discussion on using image analysis on historical CCTV image to better link with ZeMus project <p>Below are examples of the full-scale pipe defects that have been previously manufactured at IKT.</p>

Figure 3 - Examples of full-scale pipe section containing specific defects that have been manufactured at IKT.

<p>Main achievements and challenges:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU project proposal concept note developed and circulated to potential partners. • Exchange of information on automated techniques for defect identification. Exchange of knowledge about requirements for automated image processing • Exchange of information on physical testing/inspection of full-scale sewers pipes
<p>Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services</p>	<p>Both partners developed a better appreciated their capability to lead EU funding bids and to better understand the EU funding landscape and how it may be possible to improve links with UK water utilities.</p> <p>Lessons were learned regarding how to manufacture pipe defects and how results from full scale defect testing could be interpreted.</p> <p>The potential and challenges for using image analysis in the historical CCTV data were identified.</p>

2.5. UDC to AaU (October 2022)

From (dd/mm/yy):	24/10/2022
To (dd/mm/yy):	28/10/2022
Duration (in days):	3
Purpose of the mission:	The installation of LSPIV equipment in the Aalborg retention pond is a milestone within the Joint Research Activities of Co-UDlabs project. This activity was carried out from 24/10/2022 to 28/10/2022 during the visit of Juan Naves (University of A Coruña - UDC) to Aalborg University (AAU)Co-UDlabs team. The visit was carried out in the scope of the Networking Activity WP2 (Capacity building), which foster the scientific collaboration between Co-UDlabs Partners.
Planned activities:	<p><u>Day 1 - Tuesday, 25th October 2022</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planification meeting. Jesper E. Nielsen (AAU) and Juan Naves (UDC) • Design and fabrication of pieces for protective hermetic boxes • Visit to AAU retention pond <p><u>Day 2- Wednesday, 26th October 2022</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assembly of equipment • Preliminary test and tuning of cameras in the facility <p><u>Day 3- Thursday, 27th October 2022</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planification meeting. Jesper E. Nielsen (AaU) and Juan Naves (UDC) • Definitive installation of cameras and calibration • Experiments (inlet and outlet sections)
Main achievements and challenges:	<p><u>Installation of LSPIV</u></p> <p>The first step of the activity was protecting the equipment from the rain and other elements. The required equipment to use the LSPIV technique in the retention pond consisted of 3 NOIR Picameras V2.1 controlled by Raspberries Pi 4. The raspberries record, storage and transmit the videos to be processed via Wi-Fi. To do this, hermetic protective boxes were adapted with 3D-printed pieces to mount the cameras and keep the Raspberries Pi inside. A metal cover has also been added to prevent rainwater on the lens of the cameras.</p> <p>The raspberries have been installed in the lateral of the retention tank, one recording the inlet section and the others capturing the outlet section of the tank. The raspberries and the cameras were installed inside the boxes assembled. Power supply has been provided through outdoor electrical boxes. To rectificate the perspective of the frames recorded by the cameras it has been necessary to measure the dimensions of the tank and obtain the coordinates of reference elements.</p>

Initial experiments

The first experiment performed was focused at the inlet section of the retention tank. The first camera was used, and a video of 5 minutes was recorded while 800 L of water, previously storage before the inlet gate of the facility, were introduced to the facility. Sawdust was used as tracer particles and distributed on water surface before the experiment started.

Cameras 2 and 3 were used to record the movement of the particles used in the emptying of the retention tank at the outlet section. The pumps of the facility were used and videos of 1 minute were recorded during the time of emptying. When the water depth of the tank decreased, two additional video of 5 minutes were recorded to better register the last part of the process in order to analyse how velocities increased and sediment deposited may be resuspended.

Figure 4 – Pictures from the initial experiments with the retention tank at AaU

Comments:

The results of the first tests are promising and the data obtained will be analysed for calibration and validation of the CFD models. Further experiments with the cameras installed are being planned and the collaboration between AaU and UDC will continue within the scope of Co-UDlabs and this research line.

2.6. INSA to IKT (January 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	09/01/2023
To (dd/mm/yy):	09/01/2023
Duration (in days):	0,5 (afternoon)
Purpose of the mission:	1 st visit of INSA Lyon at IKT for mutual presentation and further collaboration. This visit is the reciprocal visit of IKT at INSA Lyon held on 01 September 2022 (see above section 2.6). Visitor: Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski
Planned activities:	Presentation and visits
Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction and presentation of IKT • Tour of the IKT experimental hall • Discussing cooperation INSA-IKT within Co-UDlabs and beyond
Comments:	After these two short visits, potential collaborations have been discussed and a longer visit is now planned from 10 to 13 July 2023 (INSA Lyon to IKT) to further work on i) metrology (UDMT webapp developed in Co-UDlabs) and ii) collaboration on green roof experiments.

2.7. INSA to USFD (April 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	16/04/2023
To (dd/mm/yy):	21/04/2023
Duration (in days):	4
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organising and coordinating cooperation within WP7 (JRA 2) between INSA, Deltares, IKT and USFD in detail • Discussion WP6 and WP7, more especially task 6.3 to anticipate the organisation and work • Visit the USFD facilities at ICAIR and discuss potential research collaboration • Advance the writing of a book on Urban Drainage Asset Management with specific contributions from USFD researchers • Attend the Pipebots Internal Demonstration Day • Discuss European Sewer Asset Management research network activities in relation to the JCUD working group UDAM
Planned activities:	<p><u>Day 1 - Monday, 17th April 2023</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planification of the week • Visit of USFD facilities (city center) • Work on the Urban Drainage Asset Management book • Meeting dedicated to WP7 <p><u>Day 2 - Tuesday, 18th April 2023</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting with researchers from USFD • Work on the Urban Drainage Asset Management book <p><u>Day 3 - Wednesday, 19th April 2023</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pipebots Internal Demonstration Day

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visit of USFD facilities (ICAIR) <p><u>Day 4 - Thursday, 20th April 2023</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meeting dedicated to WP6 • Work on the Urban Drainage Asset Management book • Planning future activities
<p>Main achievements and challenges:</p>	<p>Regarding Co-UDlabs work packages, the meeting related to WP6 and WP7 have greatly help anticipating future difficulties and better engage in a collaborative work. During the WP7, the discussion has been focused on the incoming tasks such as a review of asset condition grading and its improvement and how to gather inspection data (CCTV reports, videos from pipe inspections) from numerous Europe countries. The objective is to achieve a representative distribution of defects per country and for the whole Europe. Videos will be used to train and improve the tool under development at USFD . The discussion has also led to a very important consideration on the future of sewer asset management, with a shift from a (necessary but limited) condition-based approach to a (broader but still difficult to achieve) defect-based approach. The WP6 meeting was dedicated to tasks 6.2 and 6.3. The main focus was how to consider the measurement uncertainties in the assessment of water bodies quality and impact of combined sewer overflows (Water Directive Framework). Next step will be to propose a parallel approach (in relation to country-specific regulation) of this question.</p> <p>The Urban Drainage Asset Management book is edited by Frederic Cherqui (INSA), Francois Clemens (DELTA RES) and two other editors not part of Co-UDlabs. The meeting of the editors (3 in person and 1 online) at USFD has significantly advanced the book, with a first draft due in early September 2023. The visit was also the opportunity to visit USFD facilities at ICAIR and more especially the Full Scale Buried Cell Flume.</p> <div data-bbox="667 1160 1275 1617" data-label="Image"> </div>

Figure 5 - Full Scale Buried Cell Flume facility

Last but not least, the visit was the opportunity to attend to the Pipebots internal demonstration day at the ICAIR buried asset test facility, used for TA in WP9. Pipebots aims to revolutionise buried pipe infrastructure management with the development of micro-robots designed to work in underground pipe networks. The whole day was dedicated to demonstration and discussion related to the different aspects of the project: (i) mobilisation, localisation and autonomy, (ii) sensing, measurement and defect classification, (iii) communications and networking; (iv) business planning.

Figure 6 - Micro-robots designed to work in underground pipe network

Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services:

The visit allowed a significant progress on WP6 and WP7. It also strengthened the synergy within the Co-UDlabs project (better knowledge of each other's expertise and of the USFD experimental devices), and to plan each other's actions for the months to come. It also enabled the foundations to be laid for collaboration, particularly through the submission of joint research projects.

The exchanges carried out within the framework of the Pipebots project are very innovative and will also be continued in the future.

2.8. Deltares to USFD (April 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	17/04/2023
To (dd/mm/yy):	21/04/2023
Duration (in days):	4
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give an invited lecture on research on mixing and multiphase flow issues in Urban Drainage in the 2-day EPSRC workshop on ‘Mixing problems’, highlight the facilities available for this research line in Co-UDLabs. Advertising for TA options in Co-UDLabs • Discuss recent advancements in research related to new legislation with respect to CSO in the UK and their relation with Co-UDlabs activities. • Identify future options for co-operation, amongst others contributing to an update of an IWA book on sewer sediments
Planned activities:	<p>17/04/2023 Travelling</p> <p>18/04/2023 Mixing Workshop (related to the EPSRC (Grant No. EP/P012027/1)</p> <p>19/04/2023 Presenting at the Mixing Workshop (Invited lecture on Urban drainage and multiphase flows, advertise CoUDlabs TA for Deltares on pressurized systems).</p> <p>20/04/2023 9:00-12:00 Meet-up with F. Cherqui and Franz Tscheikner-Gratl on possible submissions from NTNU for CoUDlabs TNA projects.</p> <p>13:00 – 17:00 Discussion with Simon Tait and Alma Schellart on the results of their PhD student Philippa Mohan. More specifically on how her work integrates with Co-UDlabs (JRA on monitoring, policy making with respect to CSO’s)). Meeting related to WP6 related efforts.</p> <p>17:00-18:00 Meeting with Kirill Horovshenkov on extending the collaboration on acoustic monitoring systems</p> <p>21/04/2023 9:00-12:00 Meeting with Simon Tait on the revision of the IWA publishing Sewer Sediments Book’ (https://www.researchgate.net/publication/7558354_Sewer_solids_-_20_years_of_investigation). Visit to the USFD laboratories and discussion of Harmonization of protocols with Simon Tait.</p>

Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arranged for USFD to join in a EU proposal for the ageing on sewer liners successfully made it through stage 1 review in June 2024) • Made contact with various representatives from UK water industry (mainly waterboards) on the issues regarding monitoring and the opportunities offered by Co-UDlabs for joint research and education • Shared my experience with P. Mohan on transferability of scientific findings and protocols into practical applicable regulations, specifically regarding monitoring of CSO's • The challenge is to convert the contacts made during the workshop in active parties who will submit project proposals for the upcoming TA call.
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services:	Gap between science on the one hand and practice/policymaking is very wide, and this seems to be the case in the UK as well. It will be challenging to convert well founded scientific insights and doubt into practical applicable and effective policies with respect to e.g. CSO's. In that sense knowledge transfer can't be over emphasised.
Next steps:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actively motivated contact from the workshop to submit TA proposals • Incorporate USFD in the upcoming EU proposal for sewer liners.

2.9. EAWAG to UDC (May 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	07/05/2023
To (dd/mm/yy):	12/05/2023
Duration (in days):	6
Purpose of the mission:	To check if the available facilities at CITEEC (UDC) are suitable for running tests to help determine the dynamic hydrological performance of green roofs (blue-green infrastructure) over time.
Planned activities:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conduct preliminary tests with different pressure points to change the intensity of the rainfall from the generators (that initially generated 30, 50, and 80 mm h⁻¹) 2. Understand the set-up of the green roofs that are non-conventional ones 3. Establish connections with the staff and technicians to determine the next steps and the way forward
Main achievements and challenges:	<p>We conducted preliminary tests with vessels to quantify the rainfall intensities for various flow pressures (Fig 1 and 2).</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Fig 1: Rainfall generator</p> </div>

	<p>Fig 2: Vessels atop green roofs to measure rainfall intensity</p> <p>We found that we could achieve intensities up to 15 mmh⁻¹ by lowering the pressure and flow rate through the valve.</p> <p>We also realised that the available set-up was suitable for running the planned tests, albeit with certain modifications, such as removing the water storage in the storage layer of the green roofs to see the changes in water detention for different scenarios.</p>
<p>Comments:</p>	<p>We agreed that the proposed experiments could be interesting and worth exploring, so we proceeded with the tests. We also agreed on a tentative timeline for these tests.</p>

2.10. UDC to IKT (June 2023)

<p>From (dd/mm/yy):</p>	<p>12/06/23</p>
<p>To (dd/mm/yy):</p>	<p>15/06/23</p>
<p>Duration (in days):</p>	<p>4</p>
<p>Purpose of the mission:</p>	<p>Organization and cooperation within WP8 (JRA 3) between IKT and UDC in permeable pavement clogging tests. Update about the IKT TA projects in the LTF of IKT. Mutual learning about IKT and UDC facilities capabilities related with decentralized system testing, green roofs and IKT laboratory for CIPP liners. Examining possible collaborations in assets deterioration programme of IKT.</p>
<p>Planned activities:</p>	<p><u>Day 1. June 12</u> 14:00 Arrival of visitors at 14:00 15:00 – 18:00 Visit of IKT laboratories facilities. Update of TA programme at the LTF status in the laboratory. All participants.</p> <p>© photo IKT</p> <p><u>Day 2. June 13</u></p>

9:00. Revision of WP8 – JRA3 status. Initial discussion about the results performed at IKT. Jose Anta, Joaquín Suárez, Thomas Brüggemann and Marcel Goerke.

12:30. Lunch break

13:30. Discussion about the data storage report of JRA. Preparation of dataset related with permeable clogging tests developed at IKT. Jose Anta, Joaquín Suárez, and Marcel Goerke.

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17:00. Technical visit

Day 3. June 14

9:00. Discussion of data gathered during the JRA after Day 2 revision. Jose Anta, Joaquín Suárez, and Marcel Goerke.

Layout of the permeable pavement clogging slabs

11:00. Discussion about TA implementation. Next steps. Jose Anta, Joaquín Suárez, Thomas Brüggemann, Bert Bossler and Marcel Goerke.

11:30. Presentation of Linka Satellite project on assets deterioration. Possible replication at Spain. Jose Anta, Joaquín Suárez, Thomas Brüggemann and Roland Waniek

12:30. Lunch break

	<p>13:30- 17:00 Concluding remarks of the visit. Last visit to IKT laboratories. All participants.</p> <p><u>Day 4. June 15</u></p> <p>9:00. Departure to A Coruña</p>
Main achievements and challenges:	<p>Joint Research Activities</p> <p>Due to the cancellation of the initial visit of UDC in May because of the transport strike in Germany, it was not possible to participate in the development of the WP8 tests during this visit. However, during the stay the UDC and IKT teams were able to review in detail the procedures followed by IKT to test the clogging of permeable pavements. The tests consisted in developing a new test methodology based on the German DiBT standard but using the previous knowledge of the UDC in this field. Thus, the tests have been carried out for an equivalent clogging load 4 times higher than the DiBT standard and using three different types of sediments.</p> <p>The results suggest that it is necessary to develop a new standard at European level to work on the clogging of permeable pavements.</p> <p>Transnational accesses</p> <p>During the visit, the next steps to be taken by IKT for the management of LTF accesses have been discussed. The next Co-UDlabs call has also been discussed and different possibilities have been studied to facilitate the access of a group of operators to the IKT facilities for the development of studies on green roofs.</p> <p>Asset management</p> <p>The UDC is very interested in this field of work since at national level in Spain this type of work in the drainage sector is underdeveloped. The IKT team presented to the UDC team its LINKA project on the testing of new pipeline rehabilitation solutions with CIPP liners as well as the development of a new protocol for the definition of cracks and breaks. The UDC team will transfer this project to the Spanish Water Supply and Sanitation Association to see if they are interested in developing a satellite project in Spain.</p>
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<p>Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills.</p> <p>Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work for Co-UDlabs and beyond</p>
Next steps /To dos	<p>Before summer break (August):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue working on Data Storage Report of permeable pavement clogging tests • Draft the main concepts for the preparation of the Deliverable 8.2 of WP8 • Start contacts with AEAS for link project once IKT delivers more information to UDC <p>After summer break</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of project deliverable • Drafting a paper on permeable pavement clogging experiences in Europe. Possibility to prepare a technical report in different languages. • Start to organize IKT mobility to UDC by late 2023.

2.11. USFD to UDC (June 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	14/06/23
To (dd/mm/yy):	16/06/23
Duration (in days):	3
Purpose of the mission:	<p>Visit the laboratory at Coruna.</p> <p>Present current lab data collected from the A/B rig at The University of Sheffield for work and discuss the next steps to ensure the work package criteria is met.</p> <p>Discuss next steps for analysis and future work to complete the work package.</p> <p>Discuss future work for next year once WP8.1 is complete.</p> <p>Learn more about the urban drainage facilities available at Coruna.</p>
Planned activities:	<p><u>Day 1. June 14</u> Arrival at Coruna</p> <p><u>Day 2. June 15</u> 9:00-12:00 Tour of the lab facilities at Coruna 13:00-14:30 Meeting discussing contribution on WP8 and for future plans/options. USFD presented data collected to date and discussed future WP plans. Discussed options for camera-based measurements of sediments and pollutants in shallow surface flows.</p> <p><u>Day 3. June 16</u> Flight back to Manchester via Madrid</p>
Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieved agreement on the next steps for the project, both for WP8.1 and future work. • Learnt more about the facilities and projects currently going on at Coruna. • Agreed on next steps for project, including open data access on Zenodo and the direction of the project. <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Image 2: Rainfall/roof top facility, leading into urban drainage</p> </div> </div>

Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	Learnt about different urban drainage facilities and how they're used to collect data. Developed an understanding of the project's overall direction and open access.
Next steps /To dos	Regarding WP8.1, Kaeli Brazier, James Shucksmith and Andy Nichols continue to collect and analyse data from the A/B rig using different grate geometries. Deadline agreed for January for submission and open access report on Zenodo. The next steps of the project will be using sediment on the A/B rig and to quantify the flow fields of surcharging manholes.

2.12. Deltares to USFD (June 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	27/06/23
To (dd/mm/yy):	29/06/23
Duration (in days):	2
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn about the Laboratory of the University of Sheffield • Learn about administrative protocols for data collection and storage of the facilities • Learn about techniques used at the Laboratory of Sheffield • Share experience with experimental work and methods (presentations) • Discuss experience on optical vision models for the laboratory and remote sensing processing • Present the work done on the CSO dataset of the UK by USFD • Present the USFD work on different experimental works in the laboratory of Sheffield
Planned activities:	<p>28/06/2023</p> <p>9:00 – 14:00</p> <p>Visit to the ICAIR centre. James and Simon introduced to the different laboratories, experimental protocols, safety and data storage protocols in the USFD experimental work.</p> <p>14:00 – 18:00</p> <p>Visit to the USFD in-campus experimental facilities.</p> <p>14:00 – 17:00</p> <p>Further discussion around analysis of UK EDM database and options for analysis. Agreement of next steps to focus on deeper understanding of rainfall characteristics as well as utilisation of multiple regression models to explore influencing factors on CSO/sewer network performance at national scale.</p> <p>Discussion of ongoing projects at Deltares including transport of plastics in channels and urban drainage structures.</p> <p>29/06/2023</p> <p>9:00 – 12:00</p>

Presentations from Alma, Simon and James on different previous projects related to experimental work.

Presentations from Antonio on Deltares work on transport hydraulics and remote sensing.

Visit to Pipe bots postdoctoral researchers. Discussion on robotics applications on sewer inspection.

13:00 – 18:00

Danko Boonstra meets technical team of the USFD laboratories.

Discussed topics:

Conductivity probes. Design of wave level measurements (without compensation).

Pumping system configuration.

Discussion on experiences with Vectrino (Nortek) velocimeter instrumentation (Deltares is having problems with near-wall measurements).

Visit and discussion with Kiril Horoshenkov (Prof. Acoustics)

Figure 1. Vegetation roughness simulator at a USFD laboratory

Figure 2. Brainstorming on experimental design for transport of solids through urban drainage hydraulic structures.

Figure 3. Simon Tait showing us his pipe loop rig and the soil-water research infrastructure at the ICAIR research centre.

<p>Main achievements and challenges:</p>	<p>Getting to know each other methods for administering access to the laboratory. Data storage policies and safety protocols.</p> <p>Getting to know the facilities of Sheffield.</p> <p>Getting to know different techniques (e.g extraction of velocimetry from surface roughness of open-channel flows).</p> <p>Possible collaboration on the spatial analysis of CSO data for the UK.</p> <p>Possible collaboration with the University of Sheffield. Simon Tait, and Kiril Horoshenkov have experience with acoustic measurements of fluid free-surface geometries. Deltares have experience on optical measurements of free-surfaces (Background Oriented Schlieren), which would be interesting to compare.</p>
<p>Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services</p>	<p>Discussed protocols for safety and data management in the hydraulic laboratory of USFD.</p> <p>Provided feedback to the construction and calibration of depth gauges. Deltares builds its own gauges with self-referencing capacity. USFD currently uses gauges that needs a recalibration at each deployment (which is labour intensive).</p> <p>Simon Tait and James Sucksmith provided a very detailed description and demonstration of the USFD and ICAIR research infrastructure capacities.</p> <p>Antonio Moreno was able to provide a presentation detailing techniques used at Deltares for optical sensing of hydraulic processes (camera and remote sensing applications).</p> <p>USFD presented their CSO datasets and the current efforts they are carrying out.</p>
<p>Next /To dos steps</p>	<p>USFD to send colleagues to a visit to the Hydraulic laboratory of Deltares for a demonstration on methods and protocols at Deltares.</p> <p>Alma Schellart, James Suchsmith and Antonio Moreno to work on possible collaboration on geospatial analysis of the UK CSO datasets.</p> <p>Antonio Moreno and Simon Tait do a meeting with Kiril Horoshenkov. Potential collaboration USFD – Deltares laboratories to test capabilities on 3D reconstruction of water-air interfaces.</p>

2.13. INSA to IKT (July 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	10/07/23
To (dd/mm/yy):	12/07/23
Duration (in days):	2.5
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visit of IKT facility. • Discussion about Co-UDlabs WPs where both IKT and INSA Lyon are contributing. • Presentation of INSA Lyon tools (URBIS, Gepeto) for SUDs and green roof modelling. • Presentation and short workshop on UDMT (Co-UDlabs WP6). • Meetings about future TA proposals on green roofs using both INSA GROOF and IKT RIs with potential applicants (VLARIO & Buildwise, Univ. of Applied Sciences Weihenstephan-Triesdorf). • Planning next steps of work and next visit of IKT at INSA Lyon.
Activities:	<p><u>Day 1 (10 Jul 2023)</u></p> <p>09:00 Arrival at IKT (JLBK)</p> <p>09:30 Presentation (JLBK) of INSA Lyon and DEEP (TB, MG, BB, RW, KM, AA, SU)</p> <p>11:00 Visit of the IKT water hammer experiment</p> <p>11:20 Meeting (JLBK with MG) to discuss possible new experiments at INSA Lyon for WP8, Task 8.3 > appointment set with GLK</p> <p>11:40 Presentation and demo (JLBK) of INSA Lyon software tools URBIS (for SUDs modelling) and Gepeto (for green roof modelling) (TB, MG, BB). Possible similarities / complementarities with WABILA (Germany) and Sirio (Belgium) tools.</p> <p>13:20 Lunch break</p> <p>(c) photo IKT</p>

(c) photo IKT

(c) photo IKT

- 14:00 Discussion about possible collaborative work on other topics (JLBK, TB, MG), including i) odour filters, ii) H₂S production in sewers, iii) testing products (e.g. CIPP)
- 14:20 Presentation (TB, MG) of previous IKT projects (e.g. sewer throttles evaluation).
- 16:00 Debugging UDMT new code (JLBK) for WP6
- 18:30 Dinner meeting (JLBK, MG, BB).

Day 2 (11 Jul 2023)

08:30 Meeting (JLBK, TB) to review all Co-UDlabs WPs where IKT and INSA Lyon are contributing (topics and comments / conclusions):

WP1: most important task is T1.3 to propose a post-Co-UDlabs organisation to continue to share urban drainage RI (organisation, objectives, funding, etc.): INSA Lyon and IKT will contribute.

WP2: report for T2.3, INSA Lyon will contribute with information collected during Novatech 2023 session A0 and the report of the FlowBru visit on 11 May 2023.

Note: DMPs proposed in WP2 are difficult to apply before end of the experiments. Harmonization of practices between Co-UDlabs is also complex and difficult to achieve. Making Co-UDlabs data sets public has been discussed. JLBK has shown the example of the Sipibel data paper and Sipibel data set

	<p>uploaded on Zenodo (see https://zenodo.org/record/5176161). INSA Lyon is ready to share this experience with IKT.</p> <p>WP3: OK, no comment, planned work is done. INSA Lyon and Deltares launched the 2024 European Junior Scientists Workshop as a Co-UDlabs event.</p> <p>WP4: Co-UDlabs should be present during the next IFAT in 2024.</p> <p>WP5: more time demanding than initially planned. No other comment.</p> <p>WP6: IKT is not involved in this WP</p> <p>WP7: IKT already contributed significantly, e.g. with recommendations to create defects under controlled conditions. INSA Lyon had initially a low number of person-months in WP7, but more time can be devoted to it. TB should contact Frédéric Cherqui at INSA Lyon: Frédéric is interested to contribute to WP7.</p> <p>WP8: see below special online meeting about WP8 in the afternoon.</p> <p>10:00 Break and other activities for JLBK</p> <p>11:00 Meeting (JLBK, MG, TB, and Kristian Förster (KF) online from Weihenstephan-Triesdorf) to discuss the draft proposal for a TA to be submitted before 06 Oct 2023: introduction of participants, presentation (JLBK) of INSA Lyon GROOF RI and related on-going experimental and modelling work on green roof, presentation (KF) of its draft proposal, general discussion about possible experiments with GROOF and further elaboration of the TA application by KF. Sharing of documents between all participants after the online meetings (papers, software tools, etc.). First look (JLBK) at WABILA DWA tool.</p> <p>12:00 Lunch break</p> <p>13:00 Presentation and short course / demo (JLBK) of the UDMT webapp for FB, ST, and MG.</p> <p>14:50 Discussion about the TA draft proposal prepared by Vlaro and how it could be coordinated with KF TA proposal discussed earlier.</p> <p>16:00 Discussion (JLBK, TB, MG and GLK online) about collaboration in WP8, in particular to produce the T8.3 report on using soil for stormwater infiltration. Possibilities to add tests of some pollutant removal material at INSA Lyon in the pervious pavement parking RI or at the Chassieu stormwater tank RI. To be further discussed between INSA Lyon and IKT in September to make final decision about tests to be carried out (GLK and IKT).</p> <p>16:30 Other activities (JLBK)</p> <p>18:30 Dinner meeting (JLBK, MG, RW).</p> <p>Day 3 (12 July 2023)</p> <p>08:30 Global review of last 2 days activities, writing of this report, planning next meeting and next visit of IKT at INSA Lyon (planned on 27-28 Nov 2023), writing the visit report at FlowBru (for WP2).</p> <p>12:00 Other activities (JLBK)</p> <p>12:30 Lunch break and final review of discussions, decisions made and next steps and tasks for the collaboration (JLBK, MG, TB, BB, RW).</p> <p>14:00 End of the visit.</p>
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Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work • Collaboration to facilitate and coordinate Vlaro and Weihenstephan-Triesdorf (KF) TA applications for the 2nd Co-UDlabs TA Call. • Develop collaboration for Co-UDlabs WP2, WP7 and WP8.
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work for Co-UDlabs and beyond
Next steps /To dos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before 06 Oct 2023: help and assist as much as necessary Vlaro and Weihenstephan-Triesdorf (KF) to finalise their TA applications and maximise the benefits of coordinated green roof experiments to be carried out at both IKT (controlled lab conditions) and INSA Lyon (real weather outdoor conditions). • IKT visit in Lyon on 27-29 Nov 2023 for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - see monitoring and instrumentation practice at INSA Lyon - collaboration on WP7 (with Frédéric Cherqui, INSA Lyon) - collaboration on WP8 (with GLK).

2.14. INSA to AaU (July 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	10/07/23
To (dd/mm/yy):	12/07/23
Duration (in days):	2,5
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visit of AAU facility. - Visit of AAU laboratory prototypes and equipments - Discussion about Co-UDlabs WP8 where both AAU and INSA Lyon are contributing. - Discussion on INSA Lyon and AAU infiltration models. - Meeting with JV PhD student on Microplastic sources and transport in UDS. - Planning next steps of work particularly the deliverable 8.5.
Activities:	<p><u>Day 1 (10 Jul 2023)</u></p> <p>10:00: Arrival of GLK at AAU and meeting with JN, JV, MR and PM</p> <p>11:20: Meeting (JLBK with Marcel from IKT) to discuss possible new experiments at INSA Lyon for WP8, Task 8.3 > appointment set with GLK</p> <p>11:40: Presentation of INSA Lyon and AAU infiltration models. The INSA Lyon model accounts for preferential flow path. The AAU model is relevant to design technosoil for treatment purposes.</p> <p>12:20: Lunch break</p>

13:00: Visit of lab prototypes and equipment

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14:20: Discussion on the content of deliverable 8.4 (WP8) focusing on the improvement of the management of detention ponds. INSA Lyon shared their expertise on the use of PIV (particles image velocimetry) to measure the surface velocity field in a detention basin. AAU showed results on CFD (computational fluid dynamics) modelling of their detention pond. They agree on the relevance of making the comparison between PIV measurements and CFD results.

15:30: Deep explanation of the AAU infiltration model by PM. Key equations were described as well as preliminary results. We agreed to add these results in the deliverable 8.5 of the Task 8.3 led by INSA Lyon

19:00: Dinner meeting (GLK, JN, JV, RM, and two PhD students).

Day 2 (11 Jul 2023)

09:30: Visit of AAU facilities

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12:00: Lunch break

13:00: Discussion with JV's PhD student on source, analysis challenge, transport and fate of microplastics in UDS.

15:00: Discussion on a summer school organized by INSA Lyon and its partners. JN and PM were invited to be Keynote speakers. GLK presented in detail the program of the summer school. Funding possibilities were analysed.

16:00: Discussion (JLBK, TB, MG and GLK online) about collaboration in WP8, in particular to produce the T8.3 report on using soil for stormwater infiltration. Possibilities to add tests of some pollutant removal material at INSA Lyon in the pervious pavement parking RI or at the Chassieu stormwater tank RI. To be further discussed between INSA Lyon and IKT in September to make final decision about tests to be carried out (GLK and IKT).

16:30: Other activities (GLK)

Day 3 (12 July 2023)

09:30: Global review of last 2 days activities, discussion on the future collaborations. AAU and INSA Lyon agreed to collaborate on three main topics including the design of technosoil to foster stormwater treatment through infiltration processes (future deliverable in WP8), microplastic challenges, H₂S mitigation in sewer lines (INSA Lyon developed an innovative H₂S release and filtration chamber, investigations are on progress)

	<p>12:00: Lunch break</p> <p>13:00: End of the visit.</p>
Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work • Thorough discussions and building collaboration on infiltration models. • Develop collaboration for Co-UDlabs WP8. • Great discussion on Microplastic challenges with PhD students (sources, analysis, transport, interactions)
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work for Co-UDlabs and beyond (on H2S mitigation, invitation to the summer school)
Next steps /To dos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing INSA Lyon data deriving from infiltrometer to test the AAU infiltration model (will be done in the future). • Draft of the deliverable 8.5 (WP8, Task 8.3)

2.15. EAWAG to UDC (September 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	18/09/23
To (dd/mm/yy):	18/10/23
Duration (in days):	30
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To prepare the tests to determine the dynamic hydrological performance of green roofs (blue-green infrastructure) over time and to understand their behaviour for different interventions (surface sealing by leaves, clogging by sand, and creating macropores to simulate root maturity) • Strategic collaboration on the blue-green campus initiative at Eawag. UDC's extensive experience to enhance our green roof and campus projects at Eawag/EMPA.
Activities:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discussion green roof infrastructure and the rainfall generator to conduct the planned tests 2. Prepare all the sensors (soil moisture and tipping buckets) to make the necessary measurements. 3. Procure and prepare all the materials for the planned tests (dried leaves, purchase sand, ...) 4. Detailed experimental design (Fig 1) 5. Strategic discussions on Blue-Green Campus at Eawag, experience of UDC in BGI planning and relation to long-term hydrological performance 6. Discuss vision of Blue-Green campus at Eawag/EMPA (Fig. 3)

Fig 1: A schematic of the planned tests

Main achievements and challenges:

Achievements:

We developed the green roofs experimental plan, which will be achieved by modifying the system to measure the underdrain and overland flows using tipping buckets. The modifications will include minimising the role of the “storage” layer by drilling holes in the trays near the outlet and connecting a pipe to a tipping bucket to measure the underdrain flow. On the other hand, the three sides of the box holding the green roof trays will be sealed – and one side left open—to channel the overland flow, which will be then measured using another tipping bucket.

As for the tests, we will test the hydrological response for different scenarios (leaf litter and sand, as shown in Fig. 2). We expect that the water balance composition changed with each scenario.

Measurements:

- Outflow (from drain)
- Overflow (from surface)
- Soil moisture (in the substrate)

Fig 2: Overview of the green roofs with proposed scenarios

	<p>Fig. 3: Architectural sketch of the Blue-green campus at Eawag. The Blue-Green campus aims to develop as an experimental blue-green infrastructure (BG)= lab where novel climate adaptation and mitigation solutions for improving stormwater management and quality, promoting water reuse, enhancing biodiversity, and protecting public and environmental health in urban environments can be investigated.</p>
Comments	Due to delays and repeated tests, we could not perform all the planned experiments in time. So, we decided to extend my stay for three months between February and April 2024 (3 months) to complete the tests.

2.16. USFD to INSA (November 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	6/11/2023
To (dd/mm/yy):	7/11/2023
Duration (in days):	2
Purpose of the mission:	<p>Learn more about space-distributed monitoring of urban drainage and openness of urban drainage data in France (CSO data in particular).</p> <p>Learn about any developments in regulation (esp. how envisaged the increased requirement of CSO monitoring in revised UWWTD) and development in openness of data in France.</p> <p>Learn about citizens' reactions/views on CSOs/urban drainage data.</p>
Planned activities:	<p>Review work to do for Del 6.4, decide on remaining activities. Several ways that the English CSO database can be analysed, some work already done by others. Limited time in Co-UDlabs, agree on proposed analyses.</p> <p>Review ideas in paper synopsis, agree on research question, agree on information to gather and who to ask/which countries to include, decide on next steps. (feasibility ICUD paper?)</p> <p>Discuss whether there been citizen engagement/reactions following any French open data? (from OTHU?)</p> <p>Look into planned future research (e.g. Sheffield water group looking into HORIZON-CL6-2024-ZEROPOLLUTION-02 call, or ITN in this area)</p>

<p>Activities</p>	<p><u>Day 1 (6 November 2023)</u></p> <p>14:00 – 17:00 Session about Deliverable 6.4 : discussion about key ideas to be developed and included, possible overlap with WP2 to be avoided, structure of the document, proposal of content.</p> <p>19:30 Dinner</p> <p><u>Day 2 (7 November 2023)</u></p> <p>9:00 – 10:00 Other Co-UDlabs meeting</p> <p>10:00 – 12:00 Visit of the GROOF platform Visit of the OTHU SuDS facility</p> <p>13:30 – 17:00 Session about Del 6.4 (review of previous day work, writing of a Word document entitled “A global framework for D6.4”).</p> <p><i>Photo 1. Brainstorming on the role of data in urban drainage management and regulation, contrasting CSOs and SuDS. Alma Schellart, Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski and Frederic Cherqui.</i></p> <p>Preparation of a framework to prepare an abstract for the ICUD. Discussing CSO-related data collection practices and regulation in France and England, and the potential role of open data.</p>
<p>Main achievements and challenges:</p>	<p>Achieved agreement on the scope of a paper synopsis reviewing CSO data collection practices, how this data is used for CSO regulation and what role open data could play in CSO regulation. A main challenge is that this goes past traditional engineering and data collection practices and links to the realms of governance and citizen engagement. Reviewed the contents of task 6.3 and how the area has evolved since the proposal was written, and also the links this has with task 2.3. Set-up a draft structure for the Del6.4 report, which can be discussed with WP2 leader. Agreed a structure to compare and contrast data collection and how (or if) data is used for data-informed management of CSO structures and SuDS structures, and the potential role of (open) data in regulation.</p>
<p>Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve</p>	<p>Alma was shown the green roofs set-up of the GROOF facility, as well as the OTHU SuDS facility which helped to increase her understanding of the intricacies and practical challenges of monitoring the performance of SuDS.</p>

<p>the quality of our RIs and services</p>	<p>Monitoring runoff from permeable paving, at the OTHU SuDS facility</p>	
<p>Next steps /To dos</p>	<p>Alma Schellart and Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski at the GROOF facility</p> <p>Alma to circulate draft ICUD abstract on ‘monitoring and regulating CSOs and the role of open data’, and reach out to Co-UDlabs team and contacts for input. To submit abstract by ICUD deadline (15 Dec 2023) Alma to discuss proposed task 6.3 work with WP2 leader, and review and add more detail to the proposed framework for Del 6.4 and circulate a next version to task 6.2 & 2.3 team in January 24.</p>	

2.17. EAWAG to UDC (November 2023)

<p>From (dd/mm/yy):</p>	<p>06/11/23</p>
<p>To (dd/mm/yy):</p>	<p>10/11/23</p>
<p>Duration (in days):</p>	<p>4</p>
<p>Purpose of the mission:</p>	<p>Data harmonisation: Discussion sessions with UDC members (focus on data management in the RI, and in UDC overall).</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understanding La Coruna field of expertise (strenghts), and potential challenges in data harmonisation. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do they store the data? • Where do they publish their findings? • What platforms/software they use for data collection and storage? • How do they calibrate their instruments? 2. Harmonisation workshop session <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance and benefits of data harmonization (Metadata standardization, Naming conventions, Unit standardization, Data dissemination) • Demo of Renku for reproducibility, presentation of OGC standards

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussing possible case studies to show importance of harmonization and use of reproducibility tools • Review of the DMP template <p>3. Feedback session with researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current DMP (what works, what does not?) • Challenges in data collection, management, reproducibility • Discussion on standards, protocols or interoperability solutions in the UDS field.
<p>Planned activities:</p>	<p>1. Research Infrastructure Tours</p> <p>CITEEC Labs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7.11.23 Construction Lab <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7.11.23 Hydraulics Lab: STREET, BLOCK (Prabhat's experiment), BENS

SuDS Infrastructure Project:

- 7.11.23 Bioretention area, green roof model
- 7.11.23 SuDS Infrastructure Project

2. Meetings**Individual Meetings:**

- 07.11.23 José Anta,
- 08.11.23 Juan Naves,
- 08.11.23 Manuel Regueiro
- 10.11.23 Prabhat Joshi

Group Meeting:

- 09.11.23 Presentation on OGC Standards for CoUDlabs, followed by discussion.

- 10.11.23 BLOCK Facility Experiment: Collaboration and observation of Prabhat's experiment.

Main achievements and challenges:**1. DMP Current State:**

- Summary of current state:

Initially, a general DMP for the entire project was considered, but due to complexity, individual DMPs for each TA and JRA were adopted, following the Hydralab model.

Each JRA and TA within CoUDlabs project requires a specific DMP.

Online platform for creating and sharing DMPs: DMPOne.

JRA and TA requires a Data Storage Report for the project dataset outputs.

Zenodo guidelines for uploading datasets

Existing DMP (guidelines and template) and Data Storage Report (template)

- Problems Identified:

Incomplete or none DMP submissions (lack of engagement)

WP2 forced to use other DMP template than DMPOne to gather information.

2. DMP Feedback

- Problems Identified:

Deficiencies in output instructions

Confusion on data upload protocols.

Considerations about the long DMP structure and the difficulty on how to fill each section should be taken into account. Also, not a clear guideline on the required documents when uploading a dataset (Data Storage Report, DMP, etc).

	<p>Reports of bugs or restricted access in DMPonline.</p> <p>Lack of commitment to finalize or meet the requirements by Research Infrastructure (RI) managers or Technical Assistants (TAs).</p> <p>Sharepoints for each TA's are provided for storage needs, expandable as required, but not used.</p> <p>UDMT acknowledged for its design but not used due to some lack of flexibility.</p>
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<p>1. DMP Current State:</p> <p>Keep the Data Storage Report and propose an unique DMP for the project (or for the TAs in general).</p> <p>Proposing a new DMP template easier to read and fill, with selection options and all in one place. Following the Waterun Horizon project DMP template.</p> <p>The initial agreement on the TA could describe in an Annex the good practices and obligations of the researcher in each TA in a concise way, with links to tutorials or templates.</p> <p>Suggests using the simplest template, similar to Eawag's, avoiding the generic nature of DMPonline.</p> <p>Preference for managing documents in Microsoft Word due to its manageability.</p> <p>Project timeline with phases including Agreement, Testing Plan with Supervision, and Initial DMP.</p> <p>Recommendation for clarity in requirements (data in Zenodo)</p> <p>2. Renku and UDMT:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration: Jean Lucke and Mathieu are using UDMT. UDMT desktop app to be located on Sharepoint.
Next steps /To dos	<p>1. DMP Current State:</p> <p>Decide on the new DMP for next TA during the General Assembly January 2024 in Eawag.</p> <p>2. Renku and UDMT:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action Items: Select a UDMT script, such as Manuel experiment, to replicate using Renku. Confirm with Manu the possibility of replicating his Sediment Temperature scripts.

2.18. USFD to EAWAG (November 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	9/11/23
To (dd/mm/yy):	10/11/23
Duration (in days):	2
Purpose of the mission:	<p>Learn more about space-distributed monitoring of urban drainage and openness of urban drainage data in Switzerland (CSO data in particular).</p> <p>Learn about any developments in regulation and development in openness of data in Switzerland. Learn about new water quality monitoring methods developed and researched at EAWAG.</p> <p>Learn about citizens reactions/views on CSOs/urban drainage data?</p>

<p>Planned activities:</p>	<p>Review overlaps and complementarity of Del 6.4 and Del 2.3 and decide on remaining activities.</p> <p>Discuss the ways in which the English CSO database can be analysed, including work already done by others. Agree on proposed analyses.</p> <p>Review ideas for a paper related to both Del 6.4 and Del 2.3, agree on research question, agree on information to gather and who to ask/which countries to include, decide on next steps. Discuss feasibility of an ICUD paper.</p> <p>Has there been any known citizen engagement from the Fehraltdorf urban water observatory? Other case studies open data in Switzerland?</p> <p>Look into planned future research (e.g. ideas around HORIZON-CL6-2024-ZEROPOLLUTION-02 call, or an ITN in this area)</p>
<p>Main achievements and challenges:</p>	<p>Alma Schellart and Joerg Rieckermann Discussed all the ideas around the overlapping parts of the work for task 6.3 and 2.3, and generated more ideas for how to take this work forward.</p> <p>Scrutinised and agreed on questionnaire questions for 2.3.</p> <p>A main challenge is that the work on open data (CSO and other) and how this could improve management and regulation of urban drainage structures, goes past traditional engineering and data collection practices and links to the realms of governance and citizen engagement.</p> <p>Discussed ideas for a potential ICUD workshop on expert elicitation of what the ‘ideal’ performance assessment of urban drainage systems (and CSOs in particular?) should look like.</p> <p>Brainstormed and discussed options and difficulty of visually representing findings of comparisons between regulations and data collection practices, Joerg Rieckermann helped explain and translate earlier work done in this area for a German conference.</p> <p>Alma met Lena Mutzner, Fabienne Maire to learn more about their work on micropollutants sampling.</p> <p>Alma met Giovan Batista, to learn more about his work on spatial optimisation of different types of blue-green infrastructure for the reduction of CSO spills.</p> <p>Alma also met Joao Leitao, and also Pierre Lechevallier to catch-up with their respective research areas.</p> <div data-bbox="762 1451 1214 1787" data-label="Image"> </div> <p><i>Joerg Rieckermann and Alma Schellart, brainstorming on open data and the role of data in management and regulation of urban drainage systems</i></p>

	<p><i>Continuing the discussions over lunch, Alma Schellart, Pierre Lechevallier, Joao Leitao and Joerg Rieckermann.</i></p>
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<p>The level and type of data that should be collected and the ideal level of data openness to gain a ‘positive feedback loop’ between citizens, water utilities and regulators, which leads to clear improvement of surface water and more efficient provision of urban drainage systems, is a tricky question indeed.</p> <p>More knowledge gained on the difficulty of micropollutants sampling, which is helping us think about various ideas on how a future ‘ideal’ urban drainage and urban surface water monitoring network might look like.</p>
Next steps /To dos	<p>Alma to circulate draft ICUD abstract on ‘monitoring and regulating CSOs and the role of open data’, and reach out to CoUDlabs team and contacts for input. To submit abstract by ICUD deadline (15 Dec 2023)</p> <p>Alma to further discuss proposed task 6.3 work with WP2 leader, Joerg Rieckermann, and review and add more detail to the proposed framework for Del 6.4 and circulate a next version to task 6.2 & 2.3 team in January 24.</p>
Comments (if any):	<p>Since the visit, it was found that the ICUD organisation will not run conference related workshops.</p> <p>So, for the elicitation workshop idea, other options will be explored (A ‘real-life’ Miro board at the CoUDlabs booth? An online workshop?)</p>

2.19. IKT to UDC (November 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	14/11/23
To (dd/mm/yy):	17/11/23
Duration (in days):	3
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visit of UDC facility. • Discussion about Co-UDlabs WPs where both IKT and UDC are contributing. • Discussion about the results of the 2nd TA Call. • Visit and discussion about Green Roof test being performed by Prabhat from EAWAG at the CITEEC • Visit and discussion about the pilot SuDS green roofs placed outside the building • Arranging dataset – storage report for permeable pavement tests • Discussion about paper review on methods to test permeable pavement clogging • Planning next steps of common work.
Activities:	<p><u>Day 1 (14 November 2023)</u></p> <p>14:00 Arrival at UDC (MG)</p> <p>14:30 Lunch and discussion about planning the next days (MG, JA, AC, JN)</p> <p>15:30 Visit of the green roof test facility inside, discussion some technicals problems an general issues (MG, JA, JN, PJ)</p> <p>16:30 Meeting (JA with MG) to discuss the results of the 2nd TA Call and the rejected once.</p> <p>17:30 finish day 1</p> <p><u>Day 2 (15 November 2023)</u></p> <p>10:00 Meeting (JN, MG) to review the data storage report (WP8, JRA 3)</p> <p>11:00 Meeting (JN, MG; PJ) at the test facility, discussion about the test setup and tests which will be done by the EAWAG at the UDC-facility</p> <p>12:00 Literature review for article about pavements for WP xxx (MG)</p> <p>13:30 Lunch (JN, MG, PJ)</p> <p>14:00 Backing test run, Discussion measurement technique and test procedure (JN, MG)</p> <p>16:00 finish day 2</p> <p><u>Day 3 (16 November 2023)</u></p> <p>09:00 preparing the information for the meeting at 10.00</p> <p>10:00 Meeting (JS, MG, JN, AG) to discuss the data storage report (WP8, JRA 3) and the main conclusions and results. Giving a short presentation about the tests and of the results.</p> <p>12:00 Calibrating the measurement technique at the green roof facility and preparing for the next test (MG, PJ, AG)</p> <p>14:00 Lunch (JN, MG, PJ) to discuss the data storage report (WP8, JRA 3) and the main conclusions and results. Giving a short presentation about the tests and of the results.</p> <p>14:30 Repairing and Calibrating again the measurement technique Meeting (JN, MG, PJ)</p> <p>14:30 Repairing and Calibrating again the measurement technique Meeting (JN, MG, PJ)</p> <p>16:30 Discussing about paper review on methods to test permeable pavement clogging (JA, JN, MG)</p> <p>17:45 finish day 3</p>

	<p>20:30 dinner (JA, JN, MG)</p> <p>Day 4 (17 November 2023)</p> <p>09:00 Other activities (MG)</p> <p>13:00 Visit and discussion about the pilot SUDS green roofs placed outside the building (JA, JN, MG)</p> <p>14:00 Lunch break and final review of discussions and decisions made. (JA, MR, MG)</p> <p>15:00 End of the visit.</p>
Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work • Develop collaboration for peer reviewed paper about JRA3.
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work for Co-UDlabs and beyond
Next steps /To dos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • literature review for regulations and standards for testing pavements for the paper • Discussing structure of the paper

2.20. IKT to INSA (November 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	27/11/23
To (dd/mm/yy):	29/11/23
Duration (in days):	3
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visit of INSA facility. • Discussion about Co-UDlabs WPs where both IKT and INSA are contributing. • Discussion about WP8 • Discussion about the results of the 2nd TA Call. • Discussion about details of the test setup for GROOF from HWST. • Visit and discussion about GROOF and the measurement technique in details • Learning and understanding on the URBIS and GEPETO software tools • Visit and discussion about the OTHU SUDS and pavement facility outside the building • Planning next steps of common work.
Activities:	<p>Day 1 (27 November 2023)</p> <p>09:00 Arrival at INSA (MG, FB, ST)</p> <p>10:00 Initial discussion and planning of the agenda (MG, FB, ST, JLBK)</p> <p>11:30 Visit of the green roof test facility (GROOF), discussion about some technical problems and general issues (MG, FB, ST, JLBK)</p> <p>13:00 Lunch (MG, FB, ST, JLBK)</p> <p>13:30 Discussion about details of the test setup for GROOF from HWST (MG, FB, ST, JLBK)</p>

- 16:30 Finish day 1
- 19:30 Dinner (MG, FB, ST, JLBK)

Day 2 (28 November 2023)

- 08:45 Visit of the outside facility (OTHU SUDs and parking lot), discussion about some technical problems and general issues (MG, FB, ST, JLBK, SN)
- 10:00 Preparing documents, discussion about the seen facilities (MG, FB, ST)
- 12:00 Lunch (MG, FB, ST, JLBK, SN)
- 13:00 Demo of INSA Green roof simulation tools (URBIS, GEPETO) (MG, FB, ST, JLBK)
- 16:00 Coffee break (MG, FB, ST, JLBK, SN)
- 16:30 Discussion about WP8 Task 8.3.2 (test setup of soil/substrate task) (GL, MG, ST, FB, JLBK)
- 17:30 Final review of discussions and decisions made (MG, ST, FB, JLBK)

- 18:00 End of day 2

Day 3 (29 November 2023)

- 09:00 Preparing documentations and discussion of the learned points, discussions about next step for IKT (MG, ST, FB)
- 11:00 Preparing data storage report WP8
- 12:00 Other activities (MG, ST, FB)
- 18:00 End of the visit.

Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work • Develop work for WP8.
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work for Co-UDlabs and beyond

2.21. USFD to IKT (December 2023)

From (dd/mm/yy):	13/12/23
To (dd/mm/yy):	15/12/23
Duration (in days):	3
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion about test setup for WP7 (JRA 2) at IKT and USFD and planning next steps • visiting of IKT facilities and discussing test and measurement technique • Discussion about webinar “Inspection techniques” (WP 3) and planning the programme and setting the date and speakers • Discussion and information exchange about WP 1, WP 2, WP 3, WP 4 and WP 9: state and next steps • information exchange about challenges (e.g. climate change, aging infrastructure) for urban drainage in GER, the UK and associated countries (The Commonwealth) • Discussing future topics for urban drainage
Activities:	<p>Day 1 (13 December 2023)</p> <p>09:00 Arrival at IKT (ST)</p> <p>10:00 Initial discussion/first information exchange and planning of the agenda (ST, IN, TB)</p> <p>12:00 Lunch (ST, IN, TB, MG, IS, AA, BB)</p> <p>13:00 Information exchange and discussion with IKT (ST, IN, TB, MG, IS, BB) and with IKT-associated water research partner about water in an international context and challenges for urban drainage (ST, IN, TB, MG, IS, AA, BB + external partners)</p>

	<p>Figure 1: Information exchange and discussion with IKT and with IKT-associated about challenges for urban drainage</p> <p>17:30 visiting of IKT facilities and discussing test and measurement technique (ST, IN, BB+ external partners)</p> <p>18:00 Finish day 1</p> <p>Day 2 (14 December 2023)</p> <p>09:00 Discussing about deterioration assets, defects and rehabilitation techniques of sewers (ST, IN; DH)</p> <p>12:00 Lunch (ST, IN, TB)</p> <p>13:00 discussion about test setup for WP7 (JRA 2) at IKT and USFD and planning next steps (ST, IN; TB)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • visiting of IKT facilities and discussing test and measurement technique, Inspection and assessment of components of the test bench to be set up for WP 7 (JRA 2) (ST, IN; TB, MG) • exchange of information about functionality of USFD inspection technique (ST, IN; TB, MG, MK) • discussion about webinar “Inspection techniques” (WP 3) and planning the programme and setting the date and speakers (ST, IN; TB, MK) • discussion about state and next steps regarding dissemination at IFAT, planning the location of GA-meeting in 2024 (ST, IN; TB) • discussing about administration and next step of Co-UDlabs in general (ST, IN; TB) <p>Figure 2: Inspection and assessment of components of the test bench to be set up for WP 7</p> <p>17:00 Finish day 2</p> <p>Day 3 (15 December 2023)</p> <p>10:00 discussing future topics of urban drainage and information exchange (ST, IN, TB, BB)</p> <p>12:00 Lunch (ST, IN, TB, BB)</p> <p>13:00 further discussion about test setup for WP7 (JRA 2) at IKT and USFD and planning next steps (ST, IN; TB)</p> <p>17:00 End of the visit.</p>
<p>Main achievements and challenges:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • experimental setup, test programme and procedure for WP 7 (JRA 2) and functionality of USFD inspection technique in detail (• draft of the programme for the Webinar “Inspection techniques” and proposed dates to discuss it on GA in 01/2024

Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work for Co-UDlabs and beyond
Next steps /To dos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussing the draft of the programme for the Webinar “Inspection techniques” (WP 3) in 10/2023 • Construction of the test setups at IKT and USFD (WP 7) • Construction / development of inspection techniques for monitoring the tests at IKT und USFD (WP 7)

2.22. USFD to EAWAG (January 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	21/01/2024
To (dd/mm/yy):	24/01/2024
Duration (in days):	3
Purpose of the mission	Visit the research facilities at EAWAG and discuss future collaboration with EAWAG colleagues (new EU Doctoral Network proposal) on “ Developing resilience in urban water resources for a sustainable future ”.
Planned activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 21/01/2024 Arrived at Zurich at night. • 22/01/2024 Met up with Co-UDlabs team in EAWAG and attend the General Assembly with all CoUDlabs representatives. • 23/01/2024 Meeting Lena Mutzner and Mario Schirmer to discuss ideas to develop an EU Doctoral Network (DN) proposal with the University of Sheffield (USFD) as a coordinator. USFD presented a summary and objectives of the network based on research to develop resilience in urban water resources for a sustainable future. • Attended research activities together with the CoUDlabs EAWAG team. • 24/01/2024 Morning tour to research facilities, experimental sites and laboratories and return to Sheffield via Manchester.
Main achievements and challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieved agreement on EAWAG participation in the future doctoral network and discuss the next steps of the project. • Learnt more about the expertise, research facilities and projects currently taking place at EAWAG.
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	Developed an understanding of the expertise and capabilities at EAWAG regarding urban drainage facilities, water quality analysis and pollutants modelling.
Next steps /To dos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • USFD will coordinate the development of the Doctoral Network, and EAWAG will be an academic beneficiary offering projects and access to research facilities to PhD students. • Regular meetings to discuss objectives and work packages have been scheduled with EAWAG colleagues and other academic beneficiaries to develop further the doctoral network.

2.23. EAWAG to UDC (January-February 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	31/01/2024
To (dd/mm/yy):	03/02/2024
Duration (in days):	2
Purpose of the mission	Installation of the Go-Systemelektronik ISA Spectrophotometer in the UDC sewer monitoring station.
Planned activities	<p>Day 1: Thursday, 01/02/2024</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of the ISA spectrophotometer on site • Installation of the softwares on UDC computer • Knowledge transfer on the use of the sensor and its software • Setup of the sensor to collect a first set of data in the night <p>Day 2: Friday, 02/02/2023</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform maintenance at the UDC monitoring station inlet point • Loading and visualization of the data collected over night • Meeting to coordinate future WP6.1 activities
Main achievements and challenges	<p><u>Installation of the ISA sensor and knowledge transfer about its use:</u></p> <p>The ISA was successfully installed on the UDC monitoring station, as see on the picture below. A first set of test data was collected overnight and could be loaded and analysed the next day. Maria and Jose were also taught how to use the sensor and its software. After this two days visit, they are able to conduct a monitoring campaign with the sensor, as planned in the WP6.1. Future steps include installing a automatic sensor cleaning and plan the monitoring campaign.</p>

2.24. USFD to DELTARES (April 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	4/4/2024
To (dd/mm/yy):	5/4/2024
Duration (in days):	2 (James Shucksmith) 1 (Alma Schellart)
Purpose of the mission:	Learn more about remote sensing techniques, and relevance to spatial analysis of surface water quality and CSO performance analysis. Discuss optical sensing techniques, and coordinate WP8 activities on this topic. Learn more about facilities at Deltares
Planned activities:	Review ongoing work on the spatial analysis of the UK CSO EDM dataset conducted by MSc student at Deltares. Agree next steps and future work. Discuss and review progress on joint paper on optical sensing techniques WP8 (output). Learn about projects on remote sensing techniques and share best practice and key findings of ongoing work associated with urban drainage and water management.
Activities	<p>04/04/2024 11:00 – 12:00 Discussion around analysis of UK EDM database and options for analysis of relevant datasets (population, rainfall, catchment characteristics etc). Review of work to date. 13:00 – 14:30 Tour of Deltares laboratory and experimental facilities 14:00 – 17:00 Further discussion around analysis of UK EDM database and options for analysis. Agreement of next steps to focus on deeper understanding of rainfall characteristics as well as utilisation of multiple regression models to explore influencing factors on CSO/sewer network performance at national scale. Discussion of ongoing projects at Deltares including transport of plastics in channels and urban drainage structures.</p> <p>05/04/2024 9:00 – 12:00 Discussion on ongoing research activities concerned with the use of remote sensing technology. 13:00 – 17:00 Review of progress on joint paper on optical sensing techniques. Review of contributions received from co-authors and discussion regarding next steps. Review of visit and next steps.</p>
	<p><i>Photo 1. Alma Schellart, James Shucksmith, Carlo de Vito and Antonio Moreno Rodenas</i></p>

Main achievements and challenges:	<p>Achieved agreement on next step regarding analysis of spatial CSO EDM database, rainfall and other spatially distributed open data. Key challenge is to understand and robustly evaluate what value can be extracted from limited datasets on CSO durations. Agreed further in person meeting at ICUD conference in June 2024.</p> <p>Learnt more about ongoing projects and remote sensing techniques, understood future opportunities for student secondments and exchanges on complementary research areas associated with water resources and/or water quality in catchments.</p> <p>Progressed WP8 output (paper on optical sensing) with agreed next steps.</p>
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<p>Developed understanding of how to consider large scale open datasets with different scales with regression-based analysis.</p> <p>Learnt about remote/satellite-based sensing technology, opportunities and current limitations.</p>
Next steps /To do	<p>Alma Schellart and James Shucksmith to progress CSO data analysis work, building on analysis in existing ICUD conference paper. Further meetings agreed, online in April to review initial steps and in person meeting at ICUD conference in June 2024 to consider outputs of analysis and possibility of further joint journal publication.</p> <p>Antonio to work on collating inputs on optical monitoring paper and circulate draft with a view to developing a robust discussion section concerning ongoing challenges in optical sensing techniques.</p>

2.25. USFD to AaU (April 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	16/04/24
To (dd/mm/yy):	17/04/24
Duration (in days):	1
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Progressing the understanding of the interaction between the water management in urban drainage systems and water in the surrounding soil. • Learn about different experimental design to investigate these interactions both for field studies and laboratory set ups.
Activities:	<p><u>Day 1 (16 April 2024)</u></p> <p>10:00 – 10:30</p> <p>Coffee break and discussion with the wider environmental group at Institute for civil engineering at Aalborg university.</p> <p>10:30 – 12:00</p> <p>Tour of lab facilities</p> <p>12:00-18:00</p> <p>Discussion and fleshing out of what research is needed in order to determine how interactions between drainage infrastructure</p>

	<p>Photo 1. Pictures from infiltration test in cell that allows control of surrounding soil hydration.</p>
Main achievements and challenges:	Achieved agreement on the best way forward to address knowledge gaps on the interaction and places of potential risk to underground infrastructure under scenarios of very elevated and dynamic ground water tables.
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	There are lots of new and interesting sensors for monitoring soil moisture levels that can bring better understanding of risk to underground infrastructure during rapidly elevating groundwater tables in urban areas. There is still interesting field to explore for the impact of this in the transport of pollution in urban settings.
Next steps /To dos	Further investigate the problem of high groundwater tables and the potential interaction between this and sustainable urban drainage solutions for storm water management

2.26. UDC to DELTARES (April 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	22/04/24
To (dd/mm/yy):	25/04/24
Duration (in days):	3,5
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visit to DEL facility. • Discussion about common work on Co-UDlabs WP8. • Work and planning optical monitoring review article. • Planning sewer flow monitoring experimental campaign using optical techniques.
Activities:	<p>Day 1 (22 April 2024)</p> <p>09:00 Arrival at DEL (JN)</p> <p>09:30 Short discussion on the visit agenda and content (JN, AMR, FC)</p> <p>10:00 Presentation of UDC work on Large-Scale particle imaging velocimetry (JN)</p> <p>11:00 Presentation of Anders N. Lofald MSc Thesis on using optical velocimetry to detect Illicit Inflow to Sewers (FC)</p> <p>12:00 Lunch break</p> <p>13:00 Tour visit to DEL laboratory (JN, FC)</p> <p>14:30 Presentation of DEL previous work on optical techniques (AMR)</p>

16:00 Preliminary discussion on future collaboration within Co-UDlabs WP8 (JN, AMR, FC)

Day 2 (23 April 2024)

09:00 FATracker 2 cameras used in a previous project were used as a reference to discuss the camera setup for the new planned experimental campaign. The status of the camera after 1 year in the sewer system was characterized to be included in the review paper.

11:00 Planning new joint research activity (part 1). Discussion of experimental matrix and preparation of initial plan for experimental campaign on optical monitoring (AMR, FC, JN)

12:00 Lunch break

13:00 Planning new joint research activity (part 2). Work on processing examples of sewer flow examples and sharing of image velocimetry codes. (AMR, FC, JN).

15:30 Other activities

18:30 Dinner meeting (JN, AMR).

Day 3 (24 April 2024)

09:00 Other activities.

10:00 Work on optical monitoring review paper. Pooling the contributions of the different Co-UDlabs partners and unifying the bibliography. (AMR, JN)

12:00 Lunch break.

12:30 Work on optical monitoring review paper towards the first draft. (AMR, FC, JN)

18:30 Dinner meeting (FC, JN, AMR).

Day 4 (25 April 2024)

09:00 Global review of activities, writing of this report (AMR, FC, JN).

	12:00 Lunch break and final review of discussions, decisions made and next steps (AMR, FC, JN). 13:00 End of the visit
Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills and reinforcing partnership and collaborative work • Joint work on optical flow monitoring planned within WP8. • Significant progress on optical monitoring review paper achieved.
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work for Co-UDlabs and beyond
Next steps /To dos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First draft of the review paper to share with Co-UDlabs partners next month. • Setting up experimental campaign: Blender model and hardware proposal (AMR) Code (JN) Optical sphere, new optical flow library and postprocessing (FC) Next meeting 24th May

2.27. USFD to IKT (June 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	03/06/24
To (dd/mm/yy):	06/06/24
Duration (in days):	4
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination regarding the implementation of the tests of WP 7 (JRA 2), Task 7.2 at IKT • Support and advice of UFSD on setting up IKT's test setup • Instruction of IKT staff in the use of an inspection system developed by UFSD

<p>Activities:</p>	<p><u>Day 1 (16 April 2024)</u></p> <p>Meeting to discuss the large-scale exfiltration/infiltration tests that are to be carried out in the large test cell at Sheffield, on a buried concrete pipe subject to cyclic loading. The current laboratory work at IKT involved examining the leakage caused by pipe articulation (rig in air). a portable DIC system from Sheffield was tested to see if the internal pipe displacement could be measured. Training was provided and the equipment left at IKT for the remaining test.</p>
<p>Main achievements and challenges:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test setup was built • Tests with the inspection system developed by UFSD were carried out • Test programme was coordinated • Further tests can now be carried out by the IKT staff alon
<p>Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services</p>	<p>Lessons learned: better internal patterning of the clay pipes is required for the DIC system to work. Plastic pipes have a different joint exfiltration behaviour compared to stiffer clay and concrete pipes.</p>
<p>Next steps /To dos</p>	<p>Task: implementation and completion of further tests Name: Markus Gillar/Basel Alswed Due date: 07/2024</p> <p>Task: return visit by IKT planned for September to observe the complementary tests at University of Sheffield Name: Thomas Brüggemann, 09/2024</p>

2.28. USFD to AaU (June 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	16/06/24
To (dd/mm/yy):	19/06/24
Duration (in days):	2,5
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visit the research facilities at AAU. • Discuss a future EU Doctoral Network proposal with AAU participation, based on project aiming at Developing resilience in urban water resources for a sustainable future.
Activities:	<p><u>Day 1 (17 June 2024)</u></p> <p>Met up with Jesper to discuss research progress in Co-UD labs and tour to research facilities and laboratories at the University of Aalborg.</p> <p>Discuss with Jesper and other academics (Per and Soren) in Aalborg ideas to develop an EU Doctoral Network (DN) proposal with the University of Sheffield (USFD) as a coordinator. USFD presented a summary, and objectives of the network based on research to develop resilience in urban water resources for a sustainable future.</p> <p><u>Day 3 (19 June 2024)</u></p> <p>Return to Sheffield via Manchester</p>
Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieved agreement on AAU participation in the future doctoral network and discuss the next steps of the project. • Learnt more about the expertise, research facilities and projects currently taking place at AAU

Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	Developed an understanding of the expertise and capabilities at AAU regarding urban drainage facilities, water quality analysis and pollutants modelling.
Next steps /To dos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • USFD will coordinate the development of the Doctoral Network, and AAU will be an academic beneficiary offering research projects and access to research facilities to at least two PhD students. • Regular meetings to discuss objectives and work packages have been scheduled with AAU colleagues and other academics to develop further the doctoral network.

2.29. IKT to EAWAG (September 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	02/09/24
To (dd/mm/yy):	03/09/24
Duration (in days):	2
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information and knowledge exchange • Coordination of the next work steps in WP 2 • Discussing opportunities for ongoing collaboration after the completion of Co-UDlabs
Activities:	<p><u>Day 1 (2 September 2024)</u></p> <p>09:00 Arrival at EAWAG (BO, BR)</p> <p>09:00 Brief introduction, initial discussion, first information exchange (BO, BR, RI)</p> <p>09:30 WP2-update and discussion (BO, BR, RI, CH)</p> <p>RI presents the status of the survey about CSO monitoring (dispatch of the survey, returns and answers)</p> <p>CH presents big topics of data harmonisation (WP 2), which are of interests for Co-UDlabs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reproducibility in Research • Data/Metadata standards • Ontologies and the semantic web <p>CH presents what has be done so far in WP 2, Task 2.1 “Ensuring interoperability by definition of common standards, protocols and methods”:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.1 Overview of Research Infrastructure and sensors • Meeting with Ana-Claudia Sima (expert in LLM and Ontologies) • Harmonizing monitoring data from a large EU-Project, possibly updating/enriching existing ontologies • Capturing and grouping the data from the DMP <p>Next steps of WP2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capturing and grouping the data from the DMP: IKT will send the DMP-data from running JRA and TA of IKT as soon as possible. IKT’s TA-project “Swedish Test Standard” (RISE) and IKT’s tests on deterioration assets within JRA2 have just been finished and the DMP’s will be send to EAWAG. IKT’s TA-project “A novel manhole” (LJMU) is in preparation now. The test will be

implemented in November/December 2024. The DMP about this project will be sent to EAWAG at the latest in January 2025.

- **Survey on CSO monitoring:**

IKT will distribute the survey via IKT's network organisation "KomNetABWASSER" with its 183 Network Operators (Public waste water companies) as soon as possible (email and eNewsletter). In order to get as much feedback as possible, this will also be discussed again in the next meeting of the KOMNETABWASSER.

- **Deliverable D2.5 "Report on smart governance and public access to data.":** Eawag is responsible for the Deliverable D2.5 on smart governance.

A first version of the Report will be prepared until the end of September and then constantly supplemented with the information (answers of the survey). To date, we have mostly answers from Swiss operators and further action is needed to generate additional responses from the Partner countries, such as Germany, to have a more balanced picture.

11:00 **IKT Seminar "IKT and the role of urban drainage (companies) in heavy rainfall events"** (BO, BR, RI, LE, GA and others)

BO presents the structure, tasks, partners and facilities of IKT – Institute for Underground at EAWAG. BO presents IKT's projects with the focus on the role of urban drainage (companies) in heavy rainfall events. Types of water / measures of events are explained: Groundwater, Sewage/seepage, heavy rainfall, water from adjacent areas, river flood and technical solutions to protect properties against flooding.

Results / Discussion:

It becomes clear, that there is often no money in Germany for measures that go beyond conventional wastewater and stormwater disposal. Only these measures are covered by the wastewater fees in Germany. In the future, however, financing options must also be created in order to be able to pay for measures like flood protection.

12:00 Lunch

13:00 **Urban living labs** (GA, BO, BR)

GA presents different projects of EAWAG regarding urban living labs. There is no fixed definition, but Urban living labs are bringing different stakeholders together. Ecological, economic and social aspects play a role in these projects. Urban observatory projects are aimed in particular at the long-term monitoring of observation areas

Results / Discussion:

The terms "Urban observatory" and "urban living lab" also lend themselves to IKT research, as we have been working with practitioners and different stakeholders for a long time.

14:00 **EAWAG Laboratory, guided Tour** (BOE, RI, GA, BO, BR)

- BOE and RI present the EAWAG laboratory “Versuchshalle” (HALL) for wastewater treatment.
- Discussing about research projects, type of funding, financial administration and clients.

16:30 VSA activities

MOE and RO present the activities of the Association of Swiss Wastewater and Water Protection Experts (Verband Schweizer Abwasser- und Gewässerschutzfachleute):

- Standardization
- Training and events
- Initiation and support of research projects
- Certification of rehabilitation systems

Results / Discussion:

Cooperation in the field of training between IKT and SVA is being discussed

Day 2 (3 September 2024)

09:15 Urban flooding / hydroinformatics (LE, BO, BR, RI)

LE presents his work regarding urban flooding/hydrology, hydraulic modelling and the data management associated with this.

Results / Discussion:

IKT plans to build a heavy rainfall lab facility with a data hub. IKT has no expertise on the filed data management. For the implementation of the data hub IKT needs support. This is where a cooperation between IKT and EAWAG comes in. There is a need for further talks between IKT and EAWAG to clarify details IKT will refer to the Co-UDlabs and EAWAG support if such references are need during the current investment application process.

According to RI there is an EU open call about “European data space for smart communities”. The 2nd round will be closed at November 30. This call could be of interest for the Co-UDlabs partners. It should be clarified who can take the lead. IKT won’t take the lead due to lack of experience.

	<p>11:00 Re-use NEST, guided tour (CO, BO, BR) CO guides through the NEST building and explains the functionality of this building regarding waste water disposal (decentralized solution for treatment).</p> <p>13:00 Lunch</p> <p>13:30 Intelligent network operations RI presents his work at the department “Urban Water Management” at EAWAG, e. g. using robust, low cost sensors for sewer network control and management, impact of the sewer system on the treatment plants.</p>
<p>Main achievements and challenges:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • new ideas for cooperation approaches between IKT and EAWAG regarding data management • procedure in implementing the survey of WP2 (details) • a better understanding of each other’s expertise • new ideas for cooperation between VSA and IKT regarding practical education of sewer operators (VSA-Weiterbildungsangebot)
<p>Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services</p>	<p>A better understanding of each other’s expertise to foster cooperation between IKT and EAWAG</p>
<p>Next steps /To dos</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IKT will inform Eawag about IKT’s data hub of the planned “Heavy rainfall Facility” and how Eawag could be involved • Discussing the call “European data space for smart communities” with the other Co-UDlabs partners • WP2: distributing the survey in Germany by IKT (recipients: 180 Network Operators of the KomNetABWASSER) <p>IKT support Eawag in preparation of D2.5 by interpreting answers from German operators and providing questions relevant for the German reality on CSO/sewer compliance assessment</p>

2.30. USFD to IKT (September 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	10/09/24
To (dd/mm/yy):	12/09/24
Duration (in days):	3
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussions of the tests of WP 7 (JRA 2), Task 7.2 at IKT • Support and advice of USFD on setting up IKT's test and discussions on future deliverable • Discussion on future funding routes • Joint planning the programme of the Webinar "Inspection techniques for monitoring underground infrastructure" (WP3, T3.3)
Activities:	<p><i>Discussing results of the tests of WP 7 and further procedure, planning the programme of the Webinar "Inspection systems for monitoring underground infrastructure" of WP 3</i></p>

Meeting an international visitor team from Japan, France, UK, The Netherlands, Australia at IKT's 30 anniversary with Iain Naismith (IKT, 10th person from right, Simon Tait (USFD, 3rd person from left) and Bert Bosseler (IKT, 2nd person from left)

Co-UDlabs project presented by Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski (INSA) with the support by Simon Tait (USFD)

Main achievements and challenges:

- Final test setup for the pipe articulation tests was confirmed
- Well received presentation given at external meeting at IKT.
- Agreed to investigate the potential for use of OFWAT Innovation Fund to create bilateral application for joint working
- A coordinated programme for the webinar “Inspection techniques for monitoring underground infrastructure” (WP3, T3.3)

Next steps /To dos

Task: OFWAT Innovation Fund Application
 Name: Simon Tait/Iain Naismith/ Thomas Brüggemann
 Due date: 01/2025

Task: Completion of Deliverable 7.4
 Name: Simon Tait/Thomas Brüggemann, 10/2024

Task: coordinating a date for the webinar “Inspection techniques for monitoring underground infrastructure”, consultation with potential speakers, promoting the webinar
 Name: Thomas Brüggemann/Iain Naismith/Simon Tait
 Due date: 10-12/2024

2.31. INSA to IKT (September 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	10/09/24
To (dd/mm/yy):	12/09/24
Duration (in days):	2,5
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to the IKT 30th anniversary international conference “Sewers for the 21st Century - II”. • Presentation of the Co-UDlabs project to the above conference. • Visit of the experimental green roof pilots for the Co-UDlabs TA Indoor-Grasp. • Last details for the TA Indoor-Grasp user group visit in Lyon on 16-17 Sep 2024.
Activities:	<p><u>Day 1 (10 Sep 2024)</u></p> <p>15:00 Arrival in Gelsenkirchen</p> <p>16:00 Visit of the suppliers’ exhibition at the IKT German conference held in Hans-Sachs-Haus in Gelsenkirchen</p> <div data-bbox="705 842 1238 1196" data-label="Image"> </div> <p>Suppliers’ exhibition at the IKT German conference (c) IKT</p> <div data-bbox="705 1234 1238 1630" data-label="Image"> </div> <p>Hans-Sachs-Haus in Gelsenkirchen (c) JLBK</p> <p>17:00 IKT 30th anniversary celebration, with presentation by Oliver Krischer, NRW Environment Minister</p>

Presentation by Oliver Krischer, NRW Environment Minister (c) IKT

20:00 End of Day 1

Day 2 (11 Sep 2024)

09:00 to 22:00 Participation to the IKT international conference “Sewers for the 21st Century - II”.
(chairs: Iain Naismith and Roland Waniek, IKT)

IKT international conference “Sewers for the 21st Century - II (c) IKT

10:10 Presentation “Key issues affecting sewerage this century – The experience from France”, by Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski (invited conference).

Presentation by JLBK (c) IKT

14:00 For the Co-UDlabs TA Indoor-Grasp (WP9): visit of the three 1*1 m experimental green roof pilots to be used at IKT for the Indoor-Grasp project (with Marcel Goerke, IKT).

1*1 m green roof pilots at IKT for the TA Indoor-Grasp (c) JLBK

16:30 The new concept for the IKT Rain lab (by Bert Bosseler

	<p>Day 3 (12 Sep 2024)</p> <p>09:00 to 15:30 Participation to the IKT international conference “Sewers for the 21st Century - II”. (chairs: Iain Naismith and Roland Waniek, IKT)</p> <p>11:50 Presentation of the Co-UDlabs project (by Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski) and of the UDRAIN initiative proposed by Co-UDlabs (by Simon Tait, Univ. Sheffield).</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p style="text-align: center;">Presentation of Co-UDlabs and UDRAIN (JLBK and Simon Tait) (c) JLBK & IKT</p> <p>15:00 End of the conference.</p>
<p>Main achievements and challenges:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of the Co-UDlabs project to a new international audience, mainly practitioners specialised in sewer asset management. • Contribution to the TA Indoor-Grasp (visit of IKT and other German participants planned in Lyon on 16-17 Sep 2024). <p>New contacts</p>
<p>Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective skills. <p>Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work.</p>
<p>Next steps /To dos</p>	<p>TA Indoor-Grasp: visit of IKT and other German participants planned in Lyon on 16-17 Sep 2024.</p>

2.32. IKT to INSA (September 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	16/09/24
To (dd/mm/yy):	17/09/24
Duration (in days):	2
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visit of INSA facility. • Discussion about Co-UDlabs WPs where both IKT and INSA are contributing. • Discussion about details of the test setup for GROOF from HWST. • Visit and discussion about GROOF and the measurement technique in details, installation of this TA • Learning and understanding on the URBIS and GEPETO software tools • Visit and discussion about the OTHU SUDS and pavement facility outside the building • Planning next steps of common work.
Activities:	<p><u>Day 1 (16 September 2024)</u></p> <p>09:00 Arrival at INSA 09:30 Initial discussion and planning of the agenda (all) 10:00 Installation of the green roof for the TA (without sedum/vegetation layer), discussion about some technical details and general issues</p> <p>12:00 Visit of the outside facility (OTHU SUDs and parking lot), discussion about some technical problems and general issues 13:00 Lunch 14:30 Visit of the outside facility (OTHU SUDs and parking lot), discussion about some technical problems and general issues (MG, FB, ST, JLBK, SN) 15:00 Presentation and Demo of INSA Green roof simulation tools (URBIS, GEPETO) 15:30 Finish day 1 19:30 Dinner</p> <p><u>Day 2 (17 November 2023)</u></p>

	<p>09:00 Preparing the rest of the green roof (sedum/vegetation layer), checking the measurement technique</p> <p>11:00 Preparing documents, discussion about the seen facilities (MG, FB, ST)</p> <p>12:00 Lunch (MG, FB, ST, JLBK, SN)</p> <p>13:00 Preparing documentations and discussion of the learned points, discussions about next steps for all partners</p> <p>14:00 End of day 2</p> <p>12:00 Other activities</p> <p>18:00 End of the visit.</p>
<p>Main achievements and challenges:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work • Develop work for common research with green roofs
<p>Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work for Co-UDlabs and beyond
<p>Next steps /To dos</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planing next visit at spring 2025. • Checking data • Doing tests at IKT

2.33. IKT to USFD (September 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	16/09/24
To (dd/mm/yy):	18/09/24
Duration (in days):	2
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information and knowledge exchange • Attending EURO-Sewer Asset management workshop incl. presentation of Co-UDlabs • Visiting testing facility ICAIR of USFD and discussing test setup JRA 2 • Discussing procedure and need for mechanical tests for asset deterioration (JRA 2)
Activities:	<p><u>Day 1 (16 September 2024)</u></p> <p>20:00 Arrival in Sheffield and discussing Co-UDlabs WP 7 (JRA 3) and project about asset deterioration at Baht Hotel (TB, YQ, ST)</p> <p><u>Day 2 (17 September 2024)</u></p> <p>9:00 Arrival at Diamond centre of USFD, registration and welcome by UDAM organisation committee</p> <p>10:00 to 15.00</p> <p>Attending EURO-SAM workshop (all), Session 1 “Deterioration modelling and strategic planning”, discussing presentations about</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KI-resilient sewer assessment of wear reserve • Optimization of wastewater renewal and cleaning plans • Deterioration of defects based on different boundary conditions • Predicting civil structure deterioration using Gompitz model • Addressing survival bias in sewage infrastructure deterioration forecast • Classification and regression models to predicts CCTV grades in Portuguese sewer networks • Statistics & ML for deterioration modelling: Gompitz and Machine Learning models • Pipebots project on tetherless, autonomous inspection robots for urban drainage pipes

TB presenting research on deterioration assets

15:00 to 17:00

Visiting test facility ICAIR at USFD with guided tour (all)

17:00 to 18:30

Discussion about Joint Research Activities JRA 2: test setup and test procedure, at IKT and USFD (ICAIR), interpretation of first results, planning next visits and information exchange (TB, GS, ST)

Discussing Joint Research Activities at ICAIR (TB, GS, ST)

Day 3 (18 September 2024)

9:00 to 16.00

Attending EURO-SAM workshop (all), Session 2 “Monitoring and condition assessment”, discussing presentations about

- Analysis of the Service life and Failure modes of Cured-In-Place Pipe sewer lines
- Vibration and acoustic measurements for condition assessment of sewer networks
- Role of condition data in asset management
- Automatic pattern recognition for CCTV
- Data-driven Machine Learning approaches for prediction of failure events due to impaired drainage asset condition

Attending Session 3 Blue-Green infrastructure”

- UDAM asset management book cooperation idea: common chapter
- Leading the way to storm water control measures asset management: how your research can feed ours!

- An analyses of failure mechanisms of permeable pavement

Final words on the EURO-SAM workshop at USFD

Group picture of the participants of the EUR-SAM-workshop: University of Sheffield (UK), IKT (Germany), TU Delft (Netherlands), NTNU (Norway), STEIN Infrastructure (Germany), INSA Lyon (France), KWB (Germany), SUEZ (France), Aalto University (Finland), Lulea University (Sweden), Northumbrian Water Group (UK)

Main achievements and challenges:

- Widening European network of researchers on the field of sewer asset deterioration
- Knowledge building regarding latest developments and research results on the field of sewer asset deterioration
- Input for the report on JRA 2 and how to describe the results and main achievements

Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services

- A better understanding of different kind of approaches to predict sewer deterioration
- New ideas for cooperation between IKT and USFD, especially considering the technical equipment at ICAIR at USFD

Next steps /To dos

- Planning visits of USFD at IKT and IKT at USFD for renewed use of an inspection system for pipe joints
- Writing the report on JRA 2

2.34. IKT to USFD (November 2024)

From (dd/mm/yy):	21/11/24
To (dd/mm/yy):	21/11/24
Duration (in days):	1
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information and knowledge exchange • Seeking interested partners for the future projects
Activities:	<p>Day 1 (21 November 2024)</p> <p>10:00 Arrival at Factory 2050, Uni of Sheffield (IN; AA)</p> <p>10:00 Brief introduction, initial discussion (IN; AA; ST; CR)</p> <p>10:30 Summary of Pipebots (KH)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KH introduces the pipebot team and presents the achievements of Pipebots. • Discussions on current projects going on in IKT

12:00 Series of presentations focusing on Challenges (Lessons from Nature to learn from, perspective of design), Sensing(Pressure sewers corrosion detection) and Challenges related to buried Infrastructure. Followed by panel discussion consisting of Prof. Emma Hart, Prof. Mike Lowe and Prof. Nicole Metje.

13:00 lunch: Visit to ICAIR facility

13:55 to 15:30

Research Challenges and Grant applications:

Interesting rounds of group discussions, where the participants were divided into groups for brainstorming ideas focusing on scope and challenges. And ideas for various Grants.

Main achievements and challenges:

- New ideas for cooperation approaches between IKT and Pipebots regarding pooling data as feed to the pipebots for training them.
- Challenges: Further discussions planned in next year to discuss the art and form in which data can be pooled.

Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services

- A better understanding of the current financial strategies, current expertise, facilities and scope for further incorporation of research on either side to fit in the common goals.

Next steps /To dos

- Need for further discussions internally to take this further.

2.35. USFD to DELTARES (January 2025)

From (dd/mm/yy):	20/01/25
To (dd/mm/yy):	21/01/25
Duration (in days):	2
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge exchange on England and Wales Spatial Combined Sewer Overflow data, and spatial correlation analysis methods.
Activities:	<p><u>Day 1 (20 January 2025)</u></p> <p>Discuss and agree upon synopsis of planned journal paper manuscript Visit Deltares laboratory Discussion of different spatial data analysis techniques</p> <p><u>Day 2 (21 January 2025)</u></p> <p>Brainstorming on further in-depth analysis of the England and Wales open Combined Sewer Overflow database, and further interpretation and discussion of the results summarised in Co-UDlabs Deliverable 6.4 report.</p> <p>Meeting with Carlo De Vito (Municipality of Rotterdam)</p>
Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge exchange on advantages and disadvantages of different spatial data analysis techniques Knowledge exchange and brainstorming on how to deal with errors/missing data found in the different spatial datasets Paper synopsis agreed upon
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extensive spatial datasets made open through a country's governmental data agency (e.g. environmental agency, bureau of national statistics). still encounter difficulties to 'align' spatial databases that were originally collected for different purposes. For example, the sewer catchment area shapefiles will not exactly line

	<p>up with the census data shapefiles, and not all CSO locations could be linked to sewer catchments, and WWTW capacity data is incomplete.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Different methods to link open spatial datasets, and errors/missing data found in the different datasets
Next steps /To dos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check again the coordinates to the wwtw and reallocate again to the sewer catchments, based on 2023 data Stick to analysis of 2022 CSO data Redo self-organising maps (leaving out: GVA, RainCount_6hour, built-up area, 2002 population, population density 2002) Yiqi and Carlo more clearly describe which data used/which data filtered out & why. Redo the panel 'with/without' wwtw (as up to now, 'with' means whether the CSO could be linked to a wwtw where we know the fft/dwf ratio, however, the 'without wwtw' data needs to be increased, as data missing) Then, redo the SOM, but only for the CSOs that are not at the wwtw (as we hypothesize that if there is enough capacity in the system, this would be correlated to the rain, but, if it is not correlated to the rain, then, it is more likely that the system is overloaded in dry weather flow) Plan made to finalise journal paper manuscript (follow up online meeting 31st Jan 2025, aim to submit paper early March)

2.36. IKT to INSA (February 2025)

From (dd/mm/yy):	25/02/25
To (dd/mm/yy):	26/02/25
Duration (in days):	2
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joining work of TA IndoorGRASP Visit of INSA facility GROOF and the small JRA-research of 1x1 m Discussion and analysing the data of the first measurements month Planning next steps of common work.
Activities:	<p><u>Day 1 (25 February 2025)</u></p> <p>12:00 Arrival at INSA (MG, VT)</p> <p>12:30 Lunch (all)</p> <p>13:30 Analysing and Discussion about the first month of measurement (all)</p>

16:00 finish day 1

19:00 dinner (all)

Day 2 (26 February 2025)

09:00 Meeting with further analysing and discussion of the measurement data and the further steps (JLBK, MaGo, VT, DW, KF, MiGr, LE)

10:00 preparing documents, discussion about the seen facilities (JLBK, MaGo, VT, DW, KF, MiGr, LE)

11:00 presentation about substrate testing (LE), simulating with datas from the project with different programmes (KF, MiGr)

12:30 Lunch

13:00 Visiting the green roof installation (1x1 and 3x3 m)

13:30 Working on green roof simulation tools with data from this project (JLBK, MaGo, VT, DW, KF, MiGr, LE)

16:00 Ffinishing day 2 / end of the visit.

Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working together on the data, checking all data, preparing the next month for the time after the project time. Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work after Co-UDlabs and finding a funding.
Next steps /To dos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Next visiting (after project) at TA-partner (Geisenheim) and IKT (Gelsenkirchen)

2.37. AaU to UDC (March 2025)

From (dd/mm/yy):	24/03/25
To (dd/mm/yy):	25/03/25
Duration (in days):	1
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Visit to UDC facility, meetings and discussions Learn about techniques for LSPIV measurement and IOT technology for measuring SUDS performance. Knowledge sharing on LSPIV and IOT sensor technology.
Activities:	<p>24 March 2025</p> <p>9:45 Arrival at UDC (JEN)</p> <p>9:45 Short discussion on the visit agenda and content (JEN, JN; JA)</p> <p>10:00 Presentation/discussion of UDC work on LSPIV for SUDS performance (JEN, JN, JA)</p> <p>UDC team present their research and practical work on applying Large-Scale Particle Image Velocimetry (LSPIV) followed by a discussion on applications and challenges.</p> <p>11:00 Presentation/discussion of AAU work in IOT monitoring of stormwater detention ponds performance (JEN, JN, JA)</p> <p>Focused on IoT-based monitoring systems for stormwater detention ponds. Highlighting experience with sensor technologies and the use of real-time data. Discussion on potential synergies between AAU and UDC.</p>

12:00 Lunch break

13:00 Facility visits at UDC (JEN, JN, JA)

14:30 Presentation/discussion of AAU work on determining stormwater outflow rating-curves (JEN, JN, JA)

AAU's research on developing stormwater outflow rating-curves based drone base photogrammetry and IoT data. Addressing data collection strategies, curve derivation, and their application in urban hydrological modelling.

15:30 Discussion on future collaboration and synergy between AAU and UDC

Discussing potential areas for collaboration between AAU and UDC including joint research initiatives, student exchanges possibilities, and funding opportunities.

17:00 End of day

Main achievements and challenges:

- Improved understanding of each other's activities and expertise
- Strengthening partnership and cooperation
- The visit included several in-depth discussions that were technically focused and solution oriented. These exchanges helped clarify key concepts, identify shared challenges, and generate ideas for future work.
- Monitoring SUDS with IoT sensors can face unforeseen challenges such as vandalism or damage. The extent and nature of these issues can differ significantly between countries, depending on local context and public awareness. SUDS monitoring requires high maintenance.

Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services

- Monitoring the performance of SUDS is challenging because sensors and data collection systems are rarely considered during the design and construction phase. However, performance monitoring is essential to understand whether a SUDS element is functioning as intended and to gather evidence for its long-term effectiveness.
- To monitor the performance of the already constructed SUDS, there is a need for innovative sensor technologies and measurement methods that can be easily integrated without major reconstruction. Flexible and low-impact solutions are key to expanding monitoring to existing infrastructure.

Next steps /To dos

- Continue the fruitful discussions for future collaboration, including publications, conferences, and exchanges between UDC and AAU. Explore potential funding opportunities for shared projects.

2.38. USFD to IKT (April 2025)

From (dd/mm/yy):	02/04/25
To (dd/mm/yy):	04/04/25
Duration (in days):	3
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussing and information exchange about DIC joint measurements discussions on future deliverable • Planning ongoing cooperation for the future on the field of asset deterioration • Planning joint publication on the field of asset deterioration • Attending IKT conference AI, Drones, Sensors and Robots for Smart Sewers and Urban Drainage
Activities:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presenting an optimized version of the DIC joint measurement system by UFSD • Presenting the current status of UFSD-projects regarding inspection techniques (e.g. Co-UDlabs, Pipebots) at the <u>IKT conference “AI, Drones, Sensors and Robots for Smart Sewers and Urban Drainage”</u> (April 2-3, 2025) and discussing it with an international visitor panel <p>Attendees at the IKT meeting on AI, drones and sensing.</p>
Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defined steps for ongoing cooperation beyond Co-UDlabs • Knowledge about status of international research and developments using AI, drones, robots and sensors for sewers
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better mutual knowledge of respective activities and skills. • Reinforcing partnership and collaborative work after Co-UDlabs and finding a funding.
Next steps /To dos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task: Preparing a joint paper about “asset deterioration” • Name: Simon Tait/Iain Naismith/ Thomas Brüggemann • Due date: 07/2025

2.39. USFD to EAWAG (April 2025)

From (dd/mm/yy):	02/04/2025
To (dd/mm/yy):	04/04/2025
Duration (in days):	3
Purpose of the mission:	The principal objective of this visit was to advance collaborative research activities with colleagues at EAWAG, with a particular emphasis on the joint development and implementation of simulation models to assess the impact of pipe defects on the hydraulic performance of sewer networks. In addition, the visit provided an opportunity to analyse the simulation results collaboratively and to initiate the drafting of a co-authored academic publication. Furthermore, the visit served to strengthen professional relationships, facilitate the exchange of ideas, and explore potential avenues for future research collaborations.
Activities:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conducted multiple simulation model runs in collaboration with João at EAWAG to evaluate various defect scenarios within the case study sewer network at Schaffhausen. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Held a series of focused discussions to structure and initiate the drafting of a collaborative academic paper, integrating findings from previous studies with the new simulation results. Engaged in meetings and discussions with staff and researchers at EAWAG to broaden subject knowledge and explore potential areas for future academic collaboration. Undertook a field visit to Schaffhausen, providing better understanding of the study area.
Main achievements and challenges:	<p>Achievements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Successfully executed a comprehensive series of model runs, refining assumptions and parameters with direct input from local experts. Developed a first draft outline of the collaborative research paper, with a clear division of responsibilities and an agreed-upon timeline for completion. Gained valuable insights from the field visit, contributing to a more robust and informed interpretation of the modelling results. <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Encountered software compatibility issues, as the version of the modelling software installed at EAWAG differed from the version used during model development, which required additional troubleshooting and adjustment time. Scheduling constraints limited the number of extended in-person working sessions, requiring the arrangement of follow-up virtual meetings to continue the development of the collaborative paper.
Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services	<p>The visit provided several important insights and practices that may contribute to the enhancement of future research activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Significance of In-Person Collaboration: Direct, face-to-face engagement was instrumental in resolving technical challenges, fostering creative dialogue, and expediting decision-making processes, particularly during complex modelling tasks. Efficient Paper Drafting Workflow: Co-developing the paper outline through in-person discussions significantly improved the efficiency and clarity of structuring the

	collaborative publication, enabling a shared understanding of the paper’s objectives, content, and writing responsibilities.
Next steps /To dos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete Simulation Runs: Finalise remaining set of simulation runs. • Develop Full Draft of the Collaborative Paper: Continue the drafting process in coordination with João and other collaborators, incorporating the latest simulation results. • Schedule Follow-up Virtual Meetings: Arrange regular online meetings to monitor progress on the paper and address any outstanding modelling or analysis issues. • Explore Future Collaboration Opportunities: Maintain active communication with researchers at EAWAG to identify new areas for joint research proposals, exchange visits, or workshop participation.

2.40. USFD to IKT (April 2025)

From (dd/mm/yy):	01/04/25
To (dd/mm/yy):	04/04/25
Duration (in days):	4
Purpose of the mission:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attending IKT conference AI, Drones, Sensors and Robots for Smart Sewers and Urban Drainage • Discussing and information exchange about DIC joint measurements discussions on future deliverable • Planning ongoing cooperation for the future on the field of asset deterioration with IKT • Planning joint publication on the field of asset deterioration.
Activities:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conference attendance. <p>Meetings for coordinating future tests for 22/04/2025</p> <p>Discussion on IKT hardware for sewer structural assessment</p>
Main achievements and challenges:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Return planned 22/04/2025 • Future test programme coordinated for 22/04/2025

<p>Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussions on how to measure internal pipe deformations measured using Digital Image Correlation (DIC) on unlined and lined concrete pipes. Plans made to attempt a full-scale test of DIC in a lined concrete pipe.
<p>Next steps /To dos</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Task: implementation and completion of further tests Name: Ashwini Ausek - IKT Due date: 22/04/2025 Task: return visit to IKT planned for 22/04/2025 to complete additional opportunity for measurement / testing. Name: Gavin Sailor - Ashwini Ausek

2.41. USFD to IKT (April 2025)

<p>From (dd/mm/yy):</p>	<p>22/04/25</p>
<p>To (dd/mm/yy):</p>	<p>25/04/25</p>
<p>Duration (in days):</p>	<p>4</p>
<p>Purpose of the mission:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carry out testing planned in person and online between 01/04/25 and 22/04/25 Exploratory testing to inform further development for Ashwini Ausek requirements
<p>Activities:</p>	<p>Carrying out full scale DIC joint measurements in lined concrete pipe</p>
<p>Main achievements and challenges:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Significant change in physical / test requirements (scale) First dataset for 600mm CIPP liner achieved <div data-bbox="429 1124 1410 1482" data-label="Image"> </div> <div data-bbox="429 1505 1219 2024" data-label="Image"> </div>

Lesson learnt / know how or best practice to be re-used to improve the quality of our RIs and services

- Further development requirements identified

Next steps /To dos

- Continuation of DIC device development. Increase pipe size and acquisition area.
- Further measurement and testing to be undertaken throughout 2025 and beyond CoUD project
- Next visit to IKT scheduled for May 2025